

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INFLUENCE OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION ON MARKET VALUE OF QUOTED CONSUMER AND INDUSTRIAL GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study was conducted to comparatively ascertain the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Fifteen (15) and eight (8) quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria were sampled for the study respectively. Pooled panel regression approach was adopted to establish the influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable. The dependent variable of the study was market value while the independent variable was accounting information. The key variables in the study were share price (SP), net assets per share (NAPS), net cash flows per share (NCFPS) and earnings per share (EPS). Asset turnover ratio (ATR) and equity to asset ratio (EAR) were used as control variables. From the analysis of the study, it was concluded that all the predictors of accounting information exerted positive and significant influence on market value of both quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Comparatively, it was ascertained that accounting information exerted more influence on market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria than industrial goods companies in Nigeria as NAPS and NCFPS represented accounting information. On the other hand, accounting information exerted more influence on market value of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria than quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria comparatively as EPS represented accounting information. It was*

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recommended that investment in acquisition of non-current assets should be made more in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria than industrial goods companies in Nigeria in order raise net assets per share and influence positively on market value and stringent cash policy should be adopted in consumer goods companies in Nigeria than the industrial goods companies for the purpose of raising net cash flows per share and maximizing market value.

1.1 Introduction

The reports of operation or performance are regarded as financial statements which presents the various elements or attributes of transactions (Okafor *et al.*, 2017 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). The various elements of financial statements are made up of different items of transactions that provide information to different stakeholders/management as well as potential investors. In this case, it could be said that all the items of transactions reported on financial statements of quoted companies could be regarded as elements of accounting information (Austine *et al.*, 2014; Innocent *et al.*, 2020). Accounting information and financial information are mostly used interchangeably in several studies in accounting and finance. However, accounting information is associated with accounting data, policies and reports which form the basis of preparation of financial statements while financial information goes beyond accounting data reported on financial statements to include economic indicators and other financial data reported on recognised bulletins. In this study, the concentration is on accounting information.

Fundamentally, the key elements of financial statements cut across statement of profit or loss account and statement of financial position such as revenue, expenses, equity, liabilities and assets (Ernest and Oscar, 2014 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). These five elements of financial statements are with essential attributes that could also help in providing meaningful information to users. The revenue status of a quoted company is capable of attracting or discouraging the interest of the potential investors (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). For instance, when a quoted company generate larger revenue in different accounting period continuously and increasingly, a potential investor might be interested in such company especially when profit is maximized progressively in different accounting period.

When costs and expenses are effectively managed and reduced continuously in different accounting periods, profit is certain to be maximized and potential investors will be attracted to the operation of such company (Karğın, 2013 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). When earnings are growing every year and larger proportion of retention of the profits is made for total equity to grow by the directors, the wealth

of the owners is certain to be maximised where the share price of such company might be influenced positively (Nwaobia *et al.*, 2016). When total liabilities or debts are effectively managed to reduce financial risk in a quoted entity by the managers/directors, it is certain that the wealth of the shareholders might be maximized through improvement in the share price of the company. When the composition of assets accumulated is with greater proportion of non-current assets to generate more revenue for the growth of the entity, potential investors might want to patronise such company (Edet *et al.*, 2025). Other attributes of financial statements reported under the elements of financial statements could also provide essential information to users and these include net assets, cash flows, leverage, earnings, revenue, retained earnings and dividend payments (Enofe *et al.*, 2014).

The various factors are capable of assisting investors/management to make decisions at any time in accordance with the published financial statements often made available at the end of an accounting period (Enofe *et al.*, 2014). These factors could be regarded as attributes of accounting information because they are presented on financial statements. In contemporary time, accounting information is crucial to managers and other users of financial statements because the expectation of any kind of investment is to maximize returns. Accounting information affects all aspects of organization because it involves the utilization of available resources with the expectation of generating maximum returns or profits.

Accounting information is described as information presented on published financial statements of quoted companies in different accounting periods (Davies and Macfubara, 2018). The various attributes that represent accounting information of quoted companies are capable of influencing market value of the entities at any time depending on the level of performance or effectiveness of strategies and policies implemented by the managers/directors (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). The key variables of accounting information include net assets per share, net cash flows per share, debt ratio, earnings per share, revenue growth, retention ratio and dividend per share and the ones considered in this study are net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share because they are rarely used in the previous studies in combination.

The influence of all the attributes of accounting information on market value of quoted companies might either be positively or negatively felt depending on the operations carried out from which the outcomes are reported on financial statements. Market value is described as the level of improvement in the indicators of shareholders' wealth which include stock price, market capitalization, market value of equity and price earnings ratio. The various indicators of market value are often influenced by the book value items reported on financial statements. Thus, the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted companies could be established empirically. Because of the importance of accounting information often prepared and presented on

financial statements of quoted companies by managers/directors, the assessment of the influence of the variables of accounting information on market value of quoted companies becomes an interesting area of research.

Studies have been conducted in this area of interest both locally and internationally but it appears that the empirical results presented by previous studies are inconclusive based on the variables and the time frame of these studies. In quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria, the empirical investigation of the variables of accounting information in relation to market value of the entities might bring about improvement in the general operations of the companies through effective review and adjustment of policies that have been adopted over the years. Thus, this necessitates the conduct of this study using quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria from the period of 2013 to 2024.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Accounting information and market value of quoted entities is an interesting area of research that cuts across various aspects of elements of financial statements. Accounting information is one of the reasons behind the growth of quoted companies in different countries of the world. Several studies in this area of interest have been conducted with the use of variables such as earnings per share, dividend per share and price earnings ratio to represent accounting information (Shamki, 2012; Irsath *et al.*, 2015; Rahman and Liu, 2021). The use of indicators

such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share, earnings per share (EPS) and debt ratio to represent accounting information in empirical studies are limited in the literature. The empirical results of these studies have conflicting results depending on the sectors used and the time frame selected for the studies. In most of the previous studies conducted, the selection of the time frame where significant changes have taken place on the published financial statements were not taken into consideration and this could be seen as one reason of the conflicting empirical results obtained in those studies (Chukwu *et al.*, 2024). Available studies in the extant literature concentrated on the examination of the influence of accounting information on market value of firms with inadequate interest in the comparative aspects.

Quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria, which consist of quoted consumer and industrial goods entities, have limited studies especially with the use of variables such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share to establish the influence on share price which represents market value. The accounting information often provided on the published financial reports of quoted companies is expected to be utilized effectively by managers to improve upon the performance of future operation by ensuring that the occurrence of previous negative outcomes does not repeat. By so doing, positive and significant influence of the variables of accounting information on market value is expected to be achieved.

Accounting information is also expected to direct managers on the pattern of investments on assets considering the level of profits made over the years as well as the level of net cash flows achieved.

From the published financial statements of selected quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria, it seems that accounting information provided by financial statements of previous accounting years is not adequately put to use by managers to improve upon their operations and thus, adverse outcomes are achieved to the point that investments on more assets are made while earnings, cash flows and other performance indicators are falling. Comparatively, it appears that either quoted consumer goods companies or industrial goods firms in Nigeria are performing better based on their annual published financial statements. It is on this note that the researcher is in doubt whether the variables of accounting information, which include net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share (EPS) influence upon the market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria comparatively from 2013 to 2024.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the comparative influence of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

i. examine the comparative influence of net assets per share on share price of quoted

consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

ii. assess the comparative influence of net cash flows per share on share price of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

iii. evaluate the comparative influence of earnings per share (EPS) on share price of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Accounting Information

Accounting information is described as critical information for managerial decision in quoted companies as well as other stakeholders. This is because of the roles played by accounting in business organizations for the purpose of providing accurate records about the past events that are critical for decision to be made, for correction of deviation and improvement in the wealth of shareholders (Sukmadilaga *et al.*, 2023 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). When talking about accounting information, there are two critical terms to be considered which are accounting and information. Accounting is perceived to be the systematic process of recording historical events expressed in monetary terms for the purpose of providing useful information that could guide the continuous operation of the organization (Abazu and Onuora, 2023). The provision of historical data about various transactions of quoted companies is made possible through accounting. On this note, it could be said that accounting is aimed at providing information for various users which

are broadly classified into internal and external users (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012). In other words, one could describe accounting as information generating mechanism or activities performed by set of individuals that have been trained in the field professionally to record, analyse and interpret transactions (Irsath *et al.*, 2015 and Edet *et al.*, 2025).

Accounting is also described as the systematic process of collecting, recording, classifying, interpreting financial data to arrive at useful information for the managers and other users of accounting information for decision purposes (Rahman and Liu, 2021 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). In all the definitions of accounting, the ultimate expectation is always to arrive at information for sound decision to be made in an organization. Thus, accounting is seen as a lifeblood of modern organizations because without proper and accurate records maintained in an organization, future operation of such organization might not be assured. The going concern status of any organization solely rely on the effectiveness of the recording processes maintained in an organization which incorporates the internal control system (Shehzad and Ismail, 2014; Ogbodo and Osioma, 2020). This simply means that in an organization where professional and experienced accountants are not involved, the going concern status of such company might be threatened as the information generated by accounting activities is so crucial for future decision-making and for the assurance of continuous operation of the company. When talking about accounting in this situation, the

various items reported on the financial statements are critical factors that help to provide information to managers and other stakeholders of organization.

Also, the various aspects or types of accounting are all critical in different organization because the items of transaction presented financial statements are classified as basis for deriving information. Information on the other hand is described as the processed data that could be used to solve problems or to correct deviant results in future (Shamki, 2012; Eugenio *et al.*, 2019). Information is derived as a result of collection of data as well as processing them. The processes of publishing financial statements of quoted companies are similar to data processing procedures which has to do with collection of transaction, recording, classifying and interpreting for the purpose of deriving information (Hassan and Haque, 2017). When talking about information in accounting perspective, it is simply regarded as the information presented on general-purpose financial statements published by quoted companies.

Accounting information is described as the information presented on financial statements published by quoted companies in an accounting period (Omokhudu and Ibadin, 2015). The various items of transactions reported in an accounting period are usually regarded as those factors of accounting information. This is because for a potential investor to take decision whether to invest in a quoted company or not, the historical information presented on financial statements

are crucial such as revenue position, assets accumulated, the proportion of non-current asset acquired, the level of profit made, the level of liabilities accumulated, the cash flow position and the current stock price in the market (Umoren *et al.*, 2018). These are yardsticks of decisions derived from financial statements made available by accounting information. In this case, it could be said that accounting information is information derived for decision purpose from items of transactions reported historically as a result of past events which could also affect future activities of an organization (Kargın, 2013; Bartha *et al.*, 2022). Accounting information also passes through the stages of deriving information from other activities which include “input the data collected, process the data and collect the information” (Nwaobia *et al.*, 2016).

Users of accounting information are broadly classified into two regarded as internal and external users of accounting information. Internal users of accounting information are those stakeholders that are part and parcel of the operations of organization (Edet and Umoh, 2024). They are described as stakeholders that often take part in the daily operational activities of quoted companies in accordance with the accounting policies of the organization (Kwon, 2018 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). The stakeholders that constitute the internal users of accounting information individually have diverse interests or stakes in the operation of companies. It is the diverse interests of these individuals regarded as internal users of accounting information that often make them to be more concerned about

the operations carried in organization (Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). The fundamental internal users of accounting information are managers and employees. External users of accounting information are individuals or organizations outside a firm that use its financial statements and other accounting information to make informed decisions. External users of accounting information include investors, debt holders, customers or suppliers, government, financial analysts and regulatory authorities (Der *et al.*, 2016).

2.1.2 Measures of Accounting Information

Fundamentally, there are essential variables or factors that could represent accounting information in accordance with the idea of published financial statements of quoted companies (Der *et al.*, 2016). In other words, the items of transactions reported on financial statements are regarded as attributes of accounting information as each of these indicators is capable of providing information to stakeholders or owners of companies (Tarik, 2021). These attributes include net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share (EPS). All these attributes are discussed in accordance with the ideas of researchers in the field of accounting and finance (Camodeca *et al.*, 2014).

2.1.2.1 Net Assets Per Share

Net assets per share is a fundamental factor of accounting information that usually represents the extent to which managers of quoted companies have invested the available funds

sourced from both debt and equity to grow the firms for the owners divided by equity shares outstanding (Al-Slehat, 2020 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). Net assets are often computed as the difference between total assets less current liabilities in an accounting period for a quoted company (Anuar *et al.*, 2021 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). The key determinants of the magnitude of net assets are the level of total assets and current liabilities in an accounting period. For appropriate understanding of net assets per share, it is crucial to explain the meaning of asset in an accounting. Asset has been defined by the conceptual framework of international accounting standard board (IASB) for developing international financial reporting standards (IFRSs) as the resource controlled by an entity from which future economic benefits are expected to flow into the company.

Assets are defined as those valuable properties or item of transactions owned and controlled by a company and used for the conduct of daily business activities (Edet *et al.*, 2025). In accordance with the perception of international accounting standards, an item of transaction is recognised as an asset when the cost incurred on the asset could be measured reliably and there is possibility that the asset is capable of generating future economic benefits into the entity. As a quoted company continues to use an asset, essential things to consider about the asset are depreciation, impairment and the importance of the asset. Assets are broadly classified into non-current assets and current assets (Setiadharna and Machali, 2017; Shamki and Al-Hamashi,

2024). The aggregation of the two classifications of assets is regarded as total assets.

When total assets are made up of a greater proportion of non-current assets and current assets are greater than current liabilities in an accounting period, the magnitude of net assets in such situation will be large and when the composition of total assets has a less proportion of non-current assets where current assets are less than current liabilities, the magnitude of net assets will be lower (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In a generic situation, when net assets are large, it could be said that the managers of such company are more concerned in utilizing less or minimal current liabilities or short-term debt in carrying out the operations of the entity (Harvest *et al.*, 2022 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). On the other hand, when net assets are minimal, it could be said that the managers of such firm have accumulated less non-current asset and more of current liabilities greater than current assets in the accounting period (Charlie and Edet, 2023). Larger net assets are capable of attracting the interest of potential investors because it could be viewed as a company that has less short-term financial obligations and with the larger asset portfolio, the reputation of the company in the market is assured.

Net assets per share is an accounting ratio that represents the value of assets attributed to a unit of shares of a quoted company in an accounting period (Anuar *et al.*, 2021). It is calculated as the value of total assets minus current liabilities divided by equity shares outstanding in an accounting period (Bartha *et al.*, 2022). The determinants of net assets per share are total

assets, current liabilities and equity shares outstanding. This simply means that the magnitude of net assets per share is highly defined by the value of total assets, total current liabilities and equity shares in an accounting period. When total assets in an accounting period are large with minimal current liabilities and equity shares, the value of net assets per share will be large and when the total assets of a quoted company are minimal with larger current liabilities and equity shares, the value of net assets per share will be lower. Also, when total assets are large with minimal current liabilities with a larger value of equity shares outstanding, net assets per share will be lower especially when equity shares outstanding is greater than the net assets (Boonyanet and Promsen, 2024 and Edet *et al.*, 2025).

Net assets per share is also determined by the combination of assets reported by a quoted company in an accounting period. This simply means that there is a certain combination of assets that is often expected by a quoted company for optimal financial performance attainment (Edet and Umoh, 2024). When the proportion of non-current assets is greater than current assets and the magnitude of net assets per share is large, such accounting ratio could influence the interest of the investors positively because it could be viewed that the financial health of such company is stable (Endri and Fathony, 2020). On the other hand, when the composition of assets is made up of a greater proportion of current assets other than non-current assets, such indicator might not be viewed as remarkable financial performance

recorded by the company (Enofe *et al.*, 2014). In a situation where the proportion of non-current assets is less than current assets, the value of net assets per share might not be considered as a good financial indicator achieved by the quoted company irrespective of the size of net assets per share.

Net assets per share is an important financial yardstick that could be used by various stakeholders to evaluate the financial health of a quoted company, investment analysis, comparison, decision making and assessment of risk. Net assets per share could help the managers of a quoted company as well as other stakeholders to evaluate the level of financial performance attained by a company through the use of shareholders' funds or the available capital sourced in running of the organization (Chan *et al.*, 2022). When net assets per share is high, especially when the value of total assets is made up of a greater proportion of non-current assets, such company in the accounting period might be said to be one with remarkable financial performance. On the other hand, when net assets per share is lower, it could be attributed that the company in the accounting period is with unimpressive financial performance (Chehade and Prochazka, 2022).

Net assets per share is an investment appraisal ratio mostly used by potential investors to evaluate the financial wellbeing and stability of an organization. The financial wellbeing of an organization is ascertained by the magnitude or value of net assets per share recorded by a quoted company in an accounting period (Der *et al.*, 2016). Net assets per share is also used for

comparison purpose especially for evaluation of a current price of shares of a quoted company in an accounting period. When net assets per share is higher than the current share price of a company, it could be said that the equity shares of the company is undervalued and when net assets per share is lower than the current market price of shares, it could be said that the equity shares of the company is overvalued (Camodeca *et al.*, 2014 and Edet *et al.*, 2025).

Net assets per share is an important yardstick for decision making often used by potential investors especially when equity shares of a company are overvalued. Also, it helps the existing shareholders to decide whether or not to keep holding quantities of shares or to sell the shares based on the magnitude of net assets per share reported at the end of an accounting period (Etim *et al.*, 2022). Net assets per share is also used as a risk assessment variable that could ascertain the risks associated in acquiring and holding certain quantities of equity shares of a quoted company in any accounting period. The accounting ratio could also help investors to gain better understanding of financial position or status of a company to assist them in taking decisions on investments (Ezejiofor and Aigienohuwa, 2023). Based on this analogy, it could be said that net assets per share is an essential variable of accounting information that could influence the share price of quoted consumer and industrial companies in Nigeria.

2.1.2.2 Net Cash Flows Per Share

Net cash flows per share is an important accounting ratio for investment analysis of a quoted company. Before the discussion of net

cash flows per share, it is important to clearly explain the meaning of cash flows. Cash flows are described as the level of revenue generated in cash and payments made in cash as well in an accounting period (Itan and Riana, 2021). When talking about cash flows, the two critical things that run through the mind of an individual especially an accountant is that the level of inflows and outflows generated and paid respectively is what is being mentioned (Ni *et al.*, 2019). Also, when talking about cash flows, it is often said to be the net of cash revenue generated and expenses paid by a quoted company in an accounting period (Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). Cash flows are seen as a critical or essential item of transactions reported basically in three components of statement of cash flows such as operating activities, investing activities and financing activities (Abughniem *et al.*, 2020; Nangih *et al.*, 2020). The cash flows of an entity are derived from the three components of a financial statement regarded as statement of cash flows. Cash flows from operating activities are simply regarded as the inflows and outflows of cash from the conduct of the principal activities of a quoted company (Yusuf *et al.*, 2021).

Cash flows from operating activity are the principal flows of cash expected to influence other components either positively or negatively depending on the inflows and outflows in an accounting period (Ogbeide *et al.*, 2017). Cash flows from operating activities could be computed by either direct approach or indirect approach as stipulated by international accounting standard 7 (IAS 7: statement of cash

flow). In the direct method, all receipts and payments are compared to arrive at net cash flows from operating activities before adjusting for tax payment. This approach is often seen as the most reliable method but the greatest limitation to the method is inadequate accounting information provided where the indirect approach is suitable (Hassan and Haque, 2017). The indirect approach of calculating net cash flows from operating activities is a method whereby operating profit is used where adjustment of items of current assets and current liabilities between two accounting periods are made excluding cash balance and bank overdraft (Omokhudu and Ibadin, 2015). The adjustment in items of current assets and current liabilities is regarded as changes in working capital items which are either added or subtracted from the operating profit brought down on the statement of cash flows (Umoren *et al.*, 2018).

Cash flows from investing activities are associated with the disposal and acquisition of non-current assets that could be used by a quoted company to generate revenue for a longer period of time (Hassan and Haque, 2017). This simply means that cash flows from investing activities are linked to acquisition and disposal of items of non-current assets such as property, plant and equipment (PPE) and other tangible non-current assets (Edet *et al.*, 2025). It is important to note than cash flows from investing activities are mostly concerned with the acquisition and disposal of those assets that could serve a quoted company beyond one accounting period in cash (Kraipornsak and

Poramapojn, 2021; Harvest *et al.*, 2022). In modern accounting practices from the managerial perspective, tangible non-current assets are mostly acquired and disposed and, in this case, cash flows from investing activities are made up of all the items. It is often expected that the total proceed from disposal of non-current assets exceeds expenditure from acquisition of those assets for the purpose of arriving at positive net cash flows from investing activities. Cash flows from financing activities are associated with the acquisition and disbursement of long-term funds that are linked to debt and equity in an accounting period (Ogbeide *et al.*, 2017; Yusuf *et al.*, 2021). The items of cash flows from financing activities include share capital, share premium, dividend payments and long-term debt (Nangih *et al.*, 2020). Increase in share capital, share premium and long-term debt is regarded as inflows to a quoted company which should be added to other components while payment of dividends and long-term debt are regarded as outflows which are subtracted (Abughniem *et al.*, 2020). The addition and subtraction in cash flows from financing activities often results to net cash flows from financing activities which can either be positive or negative depending on the size of disbursement of funds and acquisition of assets (Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). Thus, net cash flows are described as the aggregate of the balances of cash flows from the three components reported on statement of cash flows such as operating, investing and financing activities (Kabir, 2021). In other words, net cash flows are cash flow balance derived from net

cash flow from operating, investing and financing activities. The higher the net cash flows, the better the financial position of a quoted company. Net cash flows per share is an accounting ratio used in evaluation of cash flow position of a quoted company based on the unit of shares accumulated by the company (Hafiz *et al.*, 2022). It is calculated as net cash flows of a quoted company divided by equity shares outstanding. Net cash flows are the aggregate of net cash flow from operating, investing and financing activities (Harvest *et al.*, 2022). In other words, net cash flow per share could be calculated as net cash flow from operating, investing and financing activities divided by equity shares outstanding.

The magnitude of net cash flows per share is defined by the level of net cash flows achieved from the three activities as well as the level of equity shares outstanding. Thus, net cash flow per share could be described as the value of cash flows achieved by a quoted company attributed to the unit of shares accumulated by the company (Hassan and Haque, 2017). When cash inflows are larger than cash outflows in the three activities of statement of cash flows with lesser units of equity shares outstanding, the magnitude of net cash flow per share will be large and when the level of cash inflows is lower than cash outflows in an accounting period with larger equity shares outstanding, the value of net cash flow per share will be lower (Edet *et al.*, 2025).

The value of net cash flows per share is based on the credit policies of a quoted company. When stringent credit policies are adopted by a quoted

company, therefore, minimal credits are allowed to customers and in such a situation, adequate cash from operation is expected to be realised. Net cash flows per share is an essential accounting ratio that helps in the evaluation of cash flow position of a company, examination of liquidity position of a company, evaluation of financial health and investment analysis (Itan and Riana, 2021). Based on the importance of net cash flows per share, it could be said that the variable, being an attribute of accounting information, could influence the share price of quoted consumer and industrial companies in Nigeria.

2.1.2.3 Earnings Per Share (EPS)

Earnings per share (EPS) is a good indicator of accounting information recognised by scholars and stakeholders of companies (Khanna, 2014). Before explaining earnings per share, it is crucial to clearly discuss earnings in accounting discipline. Earnings are simply described as the possibility of maximizing profits in an accounting period. When talking about earnings, a simple meaning that could be given to such expression is that adequate profit is expected from operations of organization (Der *et al.*, 2016; Uwuigbe *et al.*, 2016). This simply means that before earnings could be achieved, maximum profit must be attained in different accounting periods. Earnings are often used to represent the level of financial performance attained by quoted companies in different accounting periods and it has several indicators that could be measured by accounting ratios and by raw accounting data presented on financial statements (Tarik, 2021). A profitable firm could

be described as one that usually declares adequate profits in different accounting periods. Thus, it is important to understand the concept of profit. In ordinary terms, profit is described as the positive difference between selling price and cost price. In other words, selling price must exceed the cost price for profit to be achieved otherwise it is called loss (Kabir, 2021).

Earnings per share (EPS) is an accounting ratio often used to evaluate the worth of shareholders in different accounting period in terms of profit generated and the equity shares accumulated (Karğın, 2013; Khanna, 2014). Earnings per share is also considered as a financial performance indicator used to ascertain the amount of profit attributed to a unit of shares at the end of an accounting period. It is calculated as profit for the year less preference share dividend divided by equity shares outstanding (Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). In a situation where the operation of a quoted company is financed by debt and equity without preference share, earnings per share is calculated as profit for the year or profit after tax divided by equity shares outstanding. Earnings per share (EPS) is of two types regarded as basic and diluted earnings per share (EPS).

The basic earnings per share (EPS) is calculated as profit for the year divided by equity shares outstanding without considering the financial instrument acquired by the company during the accounting period (Kousenidis *et al.*, 2012 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). While the diluted earnings per share (EPS) is calculated as profit for the year divided by outstanding shares and other potential dilutive financial instruments

(Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). In most cases, the basic EPS is usually used in empirical studies. The magnitude of EPS is influenced by the following factors such as profit for the year, revenue growth, net profit margin, number of shares outstanding, rate of company income tax and operating efficiency. When profit for the year made by a quoted company is large with a minimal equity shares outstanding, it is certain that EPS will be large and when profit for the year is lower with a certain level of equity shares outstanding, the EPS will be lower (Kwon, 2018).

Revenue growth could be represented by total revenue divided by equity shares outstanding or trend increase in revenue (Edet *et al.*, 2025). When revenue growth is positive, it is certain to have high level of EPS and when revenue growth is negative, it is possible to have lower EPS (Nangih *et al.*, 2020). When the net profit margin, which is calculated as profit for the year divided by revenue, is large, the EPS will be high as well and when the net profit margin is minimal, the EPS will be lower (Nguyen and Bui, 2020). Based on this factor, the EPS could be translated into net profit margin multiplied by revenue per share of a quoted company. When equity shares outstanding is large with lower profit for the year, it is certain to have a minimal EPS and when equity shares outstanding is lower with a certain amount of profit for the year, it is possible to have a higher EPS. When the rate of income tax for a quoted company is high, profit for the year will be lower where EPS will be minimal and when the rate of income tax

is lower, profit for the year will be large as well as EPS (Nwaobia *et al.*, 2016).

Operating efficiency is another factor that could influence the magnitude of earnings per share (EPS). This simply means that when an organization has a higher operating efficiency, profit for the year is certain to be maximized where EPS will be high and when the operating efficiency is low, profit for the year is certain to be low where the EPS will be minimal (Ogbeide *et al.*, 2017). For the fact that EPS is an essential variable of financial performance and investment appraisal, it therefore means that the attribute is an essential factor of accounting information to various stakeholders or users (Ogbodo and Osisioma, 2020). On this note, the influence of accounting information, using EPS, is expected to be established on market value represented by share price of quoted consumer and industrial companies in Nigeria.

2.1.3 Market Value

The owners of companies who are shareholders are always interested about the maximization of their wealth through the growth of their shares in terms of stock price. Market value is an interesting indicator that shows the level of growth or improvement attained by a quoted company at a given time (Kwon, 2018). The continuous improvement or improve in stock price of shares could be seen as an advantage to the existing shareholders as this usually help to generate more wealth as well as attracting the interest of the potential investors (Uwuigbe *et al.*, 2016). Although, as the stock price continues to increase potential investor might find it difficult to acquire the shares of the company as

the unit of shares is costly but for the existing shareholders, their wealth is maximized. For the fact that quoted companies are not run and managed by the shareholders or the owners but by the agents who are the directors with adequate business experience, it is possible to say that those directors have greater responsibilities to ensure that market value of their entities is improved meaningfully in different accounting period.

Stock price is described as the current share price of a quoted company at a given period of time. It is the rate of exchange that indicate the worth of shares outstanding for all the equity shareholders (Ni *et al.*, 2019). Stock price is an indicator that indicates how well a company is doing to maximise the wealth of the shareholders (Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). Often times, stock price is seen as a representative of the outcomes of the internal operation of an organization through the effective strategic formulation of the management (Itan and Riana, 2021). This is why in some cases the efficiency and effectiveness of managers of quoted entities is represented by the level of stock price (Shehzad and Ismail, 2014). When the stock price is low, it might be described as the inefficiency or ineffectiveness of the strategy formulated and implemented by the directors for the fact that directors are seen as agents of quoted companies entrusted with the responsibility of ensuring that the wealth of the owners is maximized. When the stock price is high, managers of quoted entities are usually applauded because of the level of performance

attained through the improvement in the stock price.

In other words, it is often seen as a situation whereby the strategies formulated and implemented and policies made by the managers have yielded optimal results to the owners. Stock price is usually considered as a single indicator that might represent market value of a quoted company as well as firm value (Altahtamouni, 2018). It is also used to represent shareholders' wealth creation or shareholders' wealth maximization (Shamki, 2012). Stock prices are of different types usually presented statistically in a stock market bulletin and these include opening stock price, closing stock price, high stock price, low price and adjusted closing stock price. Opening stock price is described as the stock price quoted by a stock exchange for a share of a company at the beginning of a period which might be a day, a week, a month and a year (Rahman and Liu, 2021). Closing stock price is the shared price quoted by a stock market for an entity at the end of operation which might be a day, a week, a month or a year (Ni *et al.*, 2019).

The high of stock price is described as the maximum share price for a stock of a company in a certain period and the low of stock price is the minimum share price quoted by a stock market for the unit of share of a firm at a given period (Ha and Minh, 2020; Kraipornsak and Poramapojn, 2021). The adjusted closing price is the stock price quoted by a stock market for a company at the end of an accounting period after adjusting for all errors. In several empirical studies, the adjusted closing price is often

utilized as an indicator of market value, firm value, shareholders' wealth maximization and so on (Altahtamouni, 2018). Stock price of a company is often quoted daily, weekly, monthly and yearly. It is often important to state that stock price of any quoted company is influenced by several factors both quantitative and qualitative factors, firm-based factors and macroeconomic factors (Buzinskiene and Rudyte, 2021). In this study, the focus is on firm-based factors regarded as accounting information represented by attributes such as net assets per share, cash flows per share and earnings per share (EPS). Thus, closing price of shares is used as a proxy for market value in this study.

2.1.4 Other Factors that Influence Market Value

Fundamentally, there are other factors that could influence market value of a quoted company and in this study, assets turnover ratio and equity to assets ratio were considered. These ratios are fundamentally linked to share price which is the representation of market value in this study. The efficiency of managers in utilizing the accumulated assets to generate more revenue is regarded as assets turnover ratio. Thus, the efficacy of revenue generated by a quoted company in any accounting period could be represented by assets turnover ratio. Assets turnover ratio is described as revenue divided by total assets in an accounting period (Khanna, 2014 and Edet *et al.*, 2025). Equity to assets ratio is computed as total equity divided by assets of quoted companies. It represents the proportion of equity used in financing total

assets of a company at any period (Irsath *et al.*, 2015 and Tarik, 2021).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Signalling Theory

Signalling theory was formulated and advanced by Spence in 1973 based on his observation on some attributes which he believed to provide signals for essential information. Based on the perspective of the author, certain attributes are indicators that could help to provide information for effective decision making and it is always expected that the parameters or indicators are provided at any time before decision is taken. The author of the theory also made it clear that it is important to understand different signals for decision making at any time. This is because there could be different signals pointing at different information which means that adequate understanding of such signals might help in effective decision making. Financial statements usually prepared and published by managers/directors of quoted companies are always with several items of transactions that are regarded as sources of information to the investors or stakeholders. The classification of various components of financial statements into the respective elements such as revenue, expenses, assets, equity and liabilities could also help to provide information for decision making at any time.

According to Spence (1973), the magnitude of items of transactions presented at the end of an accounting period for a quoted company might be a signal to vital information. This simply means that signalling theory is related to accounting information as the various items of

transactions reported on financial statements such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share, earnings per share and debt ratio are signals of essential information to investors which could also influence the wealth of the shareholders or market value of the entity. Larger net asset reported at the end of accounting period for a quoted company in different accounting period with greater proportion of non-current assets indicates that the entity is a large firm which will always generate adequate revenue and maximize the wealth of the shareholders (Etim *et al.*, 2022). With the large net assets base recorded by a quoted entity in different accounting period investors (both potential) will classify such firm as one that will always report larger revenue, profit, total equity as well as paying larger amount of dividends to the shareholders at the end of every accounting period. Such company will always provide information to the debt holders in terms of paying back the interest of the debts annually and the principal at maturity. Positive net cash flow balance is regarded as signal that could help the potential investors to decide to acquire the shares of a firm with such balance or grant loans to the company with the expectation of recovering both annual interest and principal amount at maturity (Hafiz *et al.*, 2022 and Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). A quoted company with negative net cash flow balance in different accounting periods might discourage both the existing and the potential investors because the balance of the cash flow is a signal to the investors that such company

might not be able to honour their obligations when the need arises in future.

Earnings is an essential accounting attribute or indicator that provides signal to both investors about the level of achievement or performance recorded over the years by the company (Edet *et al.*, 2025). It is also used to appraise the effectiveness and efficiency of directors of quoted companies. Larger profit made by a quoted entity in different accounting periods shows that such company is doing well especially when the greater proportion such profit is real and not just paper profit where adequate cash is maintained by the company (Ogiriki and Stephen, 2022). Larger profit recorded by a quoted company in different accounting period with positive cash flow balance shows that the entity is progressing and the interest of the various stakeholders might be protected without any form of default. This simply means that a quoted entity with fluctuating profits in some years and losses is one that investors might be discouraged because it seems such entity might not be able to honour obligations as at when due because of inadequate cash caused by losses recorded from operation in different accounting periods (Purwaningrum and Adhikara, 2022).

Based on the discussion and in accordance with signalling theory, it could be said that the various attributes of accounting information are signals to investors and the magnitude of items of transactions reported at the end of operation are crucial factors that could influence the wealth of the shareholders either positively or negatively. In this case, net assets per share, net

cash flows per share and earnings per share are signals of accounting information that provide information to potential and existing investors which might also influence market value of quoted consumer and industrial companies in Nigeria either positively or negatively. The assertion in this study is that signalling theory is related as the performance of quoted consumer and industrial companies in Nigeria reported on financial statements annually is with signals for decision making which could in turn maximize the wealth of the shareholders in terms of improvement in share price and growth in other wealth maximization indicators. In this case, the theory was adopted in this study.

2.2.2 Agency Theory

Agency theory was developed and advanced by Jensen and Meckling (1976). According to the authors of this theory, conflict of interest is always certain to occur between managers and directors of organization where the expectation is that an organization is to be run in accordance with the interest of the owners. The theory makes it clear that in quoted companies, there are agents and principal and it is often expected that the agents should carry out primary responsibilities of ensuring that the wealth of the shareholders is maximized as well as sustaining the operations through the improvement of critical factors such as share price and other indicators that support the growth of shareholders' wealth (Yusuf *et al.*, 2021). Agency theory is basically concerned with two categories of individuals known as the managers/directors and the owners. The managers/directors of quoted companies are

regarded as agents while the owners (shareholders) are known as the principals. The interests of the owners are expected to be considered prime at any point in time in piloting the activities of companies by agents.

Accountability and transparency are the essential attributes expected from the agents who are the directors. Accountability is simply regarded as a process of accepting responsibility for whatever act executed at any point in time while transparency is the process of performing or discharging responsibility in accordance with the stipulated rules or performing activities for the satisfaction of set of individuals other than considering self-interest (Purwaningrum and Adhikara, 2022). Transparency is also described as the process of avoiding conflict of interest in discharging responsibility. The principals of organization or shareholders are set of individuals that are expected to delegate or entrust the running of their businesses to set of individuals known as agents with the expectation that their interests will be considered primes and not that of the agents (Ogiriki and Stephen, 2022). There are indicators that could be used to assess the level of achievement made by the agents as well as the principals or the owners. For the agents, the item of transaction reported on financial statements at the end of accounting periods are the yardsticks that measure the effectiveness of their strategies and policies formulated and implemented.

This simply means that the extent to which attributes reported on financial statements

could provide information to the users depends on the effectiveness and efficiency of the directors/managers known as the agents. In other words, the attracting force that brings potential investors into an existing quoted company are the effectiveness and efficiency of the strategies and policies used by the managers or directors of the entity and these are replicated on the financial statements often published at the end of accounting period. For the principals or shareholders, the various indicators that show the level of achievement made include stock price, market capitalization and market value of equity. These indicators that show the level of achievement made by the principals solely depend on the attributes reported on financial statements known as accounting information indicators where the effectiveness of accounting information indicators depends on the strategies the strategies and policies of the existing directors or managers of quoted companies (Edet *et al.*, 2025).

It is on this note that agency theory is connected to the attributes of accounting information as well as the factors of market value which therefore means that the establishment of the influence of the variables of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria could be explained by this theory. Transparency of agents regarded as directors of quoted companies could be reflected on variables such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share, earnings per share and debt ratio and the direction of these attributes on the indicators of market value represent the

effectiveness of accounting information on market value which could also be interpreted as the level of benefits of agents of quoted companies to the principals or owners (Khomidah and Setiawan, 2022). Thus, the adoption of this theory in this study paints a clear picture of the responsibilities of the agents expected to be discharged diligently to the principals or owners. On this note, the theory was adopted in the study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Related studies conducted both locally and internationally were reviewed for the purpose of ascertaining relevant gap in the literature. These include the following:

Ernest and Oscar (2014) comparatively examined the value relevance of financial information in the Nigeria banking and petroleum sectors. The aim of the researchers was to comparatively study the value relevance of accounting information in the Nigeria banking and Petroleum sectors. The researchers sampled ten (10) companies in a random manner from each of these banking and petroleum sectors. The dependent variable of the study was market price per share while the independent variables were EPS, book value of equity and leverage. The period of the study was from 2007 to 2011. Panel data were sourced from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sectors and analysed using multiple regression technique. The result showed that EPS information was the most considered by the investors when deciding the share price. The result also showed that the financial information in the oil and gas is more

value relevant compared to the financial information disclosed by companies in the banking sector.

Nwaobia *et al.* (2016) examined value relevance of accounting information and firm value: A study of consumer goods manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The aim of the study was to examine empirically the importance and influence of accounting information on firm value of listed consumer goods manufacturing sector in Nigeria. The relevant variables of the study were relevant of accounting information (independent variable) measured by earnings per share (EPS), book value per share (BVPS), dividend per share (DPS), liquidity (LQ) and cash flow from operations (CFOP) and market value of equity (dependent variable). Quantitative research design approach was employed by the researchers. The study sampled twenty-eight (28) consumer goods listed firms listed on Nigerian Stock Exchange. Panel data were collected from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled firms listed in NSE. Multiple regression technique was used to analyse the obtained data. The result revealed that there was no influence of accounting information on firm value before the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). Thus, the researchers concluded that change in standards from SAS to IFRSs had no significant influence on the accounting information as a predictor of firm's value.

Umoren *et al.* (2018) studied the value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian listed financial companies. The key variables of the

study were relevant of accounting information (independent variable) proxied by earnings per share (EPS) and book value per share (BVPS) and market price of shares (dependent variable). The study was quantitative in nature because the conduct relied on secondary data obtainable from published annual reports of selected quoted financial companies in Nigeria. the purposive sampling technique was employed in the study by the researchers to choose the sample size of ten (10) banks. The study covered the period of 2007 to 2016 and panel data were collected based on the relevant variables of the study. The essential data collected for the study were analysed using the ordinary least square (OLS) regression approach. From the analyses, it was discovered that BVPS and EPS had inconsequential influence on market price per share MPS before and after the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria. it was recommended that adequate effort should be made by regulatory authorities to ensure full compliance with the IFRSs in various sectors.

Innocent *et al.* (2020) examined accounting information and stock prices of quoted manufacturing firms: Multi-variant panel data evidence from Nigeria. The study assessed the influence of accounting information on stock price of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study was conducted to cover the period of ten (10) years, from 2008 to 2017, and the population of the study was made up of twenty-three (23) Nigerian manufacturing firms listed on the floor of Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. The dependent variable of the study was accounting information proxied assets turnover

rate (ATR), book value per share (BVPS) and debt equity ratio (DER) while the independent variable of the study was stock price measured by market value. Data for the study was extracted from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled firms. The cross-sectional data obtained were analysed using various statistical tools such as fixed effect model (FEM). From the results of the analysis, it was discovered that the variables of accounting information (ATR, BVPS and DER) exerted positive and substantial influence on the stock price of the firms studied.

Yusuf *et al.* (2021) investigated value relevance of accounting information and share price: Moderating influence of corporate governance practice of listed firm in the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. The study aimed at examining the influence of accounting information on share price of firms in Nigeria. The relevance of accounting information was reviewed with some specific variables such as earnings per share (EPS), price earnings (P/E) ratio, return on equity (ROE) and net book value per share (NBVPS). The independent variable was moderated by the effect of corporate governance. The study covered the study of 2012 to 2021. However, data were not collected but the empirical findings were derived from the relevant studies reviewed and it was stated that all the variables that represented value relevance of accounting information are all essential to stock price of companies.

Chehade and Prochazka (2022) investigated value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market: The case of IFRS adoption by

non-financial listed firms in Saudi Arabia. The study aimed at examining value relevance of accounting information in an emerging market. The study was conducted to cover the period from 2014 to 2019 and ninety-eight (98) non-financial quoted entities in Saudi Arabia were used for the study. the dependent variable of the study was market value per share while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and operating cash flow per share (OCFPS). The control variables selected by the researchers were dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), leverage (LV) and industry type (IT). A dummy variable of IFRSs adoption was used in the study. Panel data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics and panel regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that the variables that represented value relevance of accounting information all exerted positive and significant influence on the market value per share of the non-financial entities quoted in Saudi Arabia.

Etim *et al.* (2022) assessed value relevance of accounting information and share prices movement of quoted consumer and industrial goods in Nigeria. The intention of the researchers was to evaluate the influence of value relevance of accounting information on share prices of quoted consumer and industrial goods in Nigeria. The variables that represented value relevance of accounting information in the study were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and cash flow from operating activities (CFO). Quoted consumer

goods and industrial goods entities were studied separately. The data in accordance with the variables of the study were extracted from the financial statements of the entities sample for the study from the period of 2015 to 2021. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics and linear regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that BVPS exerted negative and insignificant influence on stock price and CFO and EPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of consumer goods entities in Nigeria. it was also found that BVPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price, CFO showed negative and insignificant influence on stock price and EPS indicated positive and consequential influence on stock price of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Ogiriki and Stephen (2022) in a study to ascertain value relevance of accounting information in Nigerian capital market. The intention of the researchers was to evaluate the influence of value relevance of accounting information on stock price of capital market. The period covered by the researchers in the study ranged from 2010 to 2020. Value relevance of accounting information was represented by earnings per share (EPS) and sale growth ratio (SGR). Relevant data were collected from the financial statements of three (3) manufacturing entities whose shares were quoted in the floor of Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc as at December 2020. The essential data collected in accordance with the variables of the study were analysed by descriptive statistics and linear regression approach known

as ordinary least square (OLS). From the analysis, it was observed that EPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of the entities studied while SGR exerted negative and inconsequential influence on the stock price of the entities studied.

Purwaningrum and Adhikara (2022) conducted a study on does the value relevance of accounting information mediate sustainability reporting disclosures: Empirical evidence of Indonesian capital market. The researchers sought to assess the influence of value relevance of accounting information on stock price. The period of the study ranged from 2015 to 2019. Value relevance of accounting information was measured by return on assets (ROA) being a profitability ratio. Relevant data for the study were collected from the financial statements of the entities sampled for the study. Data were analysed by descriptive statistics and linear regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that ROA exerted positive and immaterial influence on stock price of the companies.

Abazu and Onuora (2023) examined accounting information and stock price volatility of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to ascertain the influence of accounting information on stock price volatility of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. Twenty-six (26) consumer goods entities quoted in Nigeria were sampled for the study and the study covered the period of 2012 to 2021. Accounting information was represented by dividend pay-out ratio (DPR), dividend per share (DPS), dividend yield ratio (DYR) and retained

earnings per share (REPS). The essential data for the study were collected from the financial statements of the entities studied. Essential data collected in line with the variables of the study were analysed by descriptive statistics and ordinary least square (OLS) regression approach. From the analysis, it was observed that DPS and DYR exerted positive and inconsequential influence on stock price volatility while REPS and DPR had positive and material influence on stock price volatility of the quoted companies studied.

Ezejiofor and Aigienohuwa (2023) assessed value relevance of accounting information and share rate: A study of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study aimed at determining the influence of value relevance of accounting information on the stock price of manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Accounting information in the study was measured by earnings per share and dividends. The study used sample size of twenty (20) quoted industrial firms on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. Relevant data for the study were sourced from the annual reports and financial statements of the firms sampled for the study from the period of 2012 to 2021. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics and ordinary least square regression approach. The results obtained from the analysis revealed that there was a positive and insignificant influence of accounting information on stock price in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Sukmadilaga *et al.* (2023) conducted a study on can accounting value relevance and pricing error influence stock price of high-technology service

enterprises? The intention of the researchers was to investigate the influence of accounting value relevance on stock price of high-technology service enterprises. Three hundred and twenty-six (326) technological service enterprises were adopted as the sample size of the study and the key variables that represented accounting value relevance were diluted earnings per share (DEPS), revenue per share (RPS) and book value per share (BVPS). Secondary data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled entities. The data were analysed by descriptive statistics and ordinary least square (OLS) approach. From the analysis, the results showed that DEPS and BVPS exerted positive and significant influence on stock price of the companies while RPS exerted positive and insignificant influence on stock price of the companies studied.

Chukwu *et al.* (2024) evaluated value relevance of accounting information in financial crisis: An intra-sector comparison. The aim of the study was to examine the influence of accounting information on stock price of listed banks and insurance companies in Nigeria. The study was conducted to cover the period from 2007 to 2010. Accounting information in the study was proxied by earnings per share (EPS) and book value per share (BVPS). Data in relevant to the variables of the study were extracted from the published annual reports and financial statements of the entities sampled for the study. The data were analysed with the use of descriptive statistics and generalised least square regression approach. The results of the analysis showed that accounting information

significantly influence stock price of the firms studied.

Shamki and Al-Hamashi (2024). The value relevance of accounting information in Iraq. The study sought to investigate the influence of accounting information on stock price of fifteen (15) listed companies in Iraq from the period of 2010 to 2020. The essential variables of the study were independent variable of accounting information represented by earnings, book value and cash flows and the dependent variable of stock price. In establishing the influence between the dependent and the independent variables, appropriate data for the study was extracted from the published annual reports and financial statements of the sampled firms listed in Iraqi Stock Exchange (ISX). Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression and from the result of the analysis, it was discovered that accounting information exerted positive and significant influence on stock price of the firms studied.

Thompson (2024) investigated accounting information value relevance in listed firms in Nigeria capital market (2011-2020). The study was conducted to investigate the influence of accounting information on value relevance in listed firms in Nigeria. The period of the study spanned from 2011 to 2020 and one hundred and sixty-eight (168) firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc as at 2021 was the population of the study. Sample size of the study was fifty (50) listed firms in Nigeria. The independent variable of the study was accounting information measured by market Value of equity (earnings per share, dividend per

share, return on equity and firm size) while the dependent variable was value relevance was the dependent variable. Appropriate data for the study were obtained from both the published annual reports and financial statements of the selected firms and Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and ordinary least square (OLS) regression approach. The result of the analysis showed that accounting information positively and significantly influenced value relevance of the listed firms studied.

2.3.1 Gap in Empirical Study

Accounting information and market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria is an interesting area of research based on the variables used in this study. Several studies have been conducted both locally and internationally in this area of interest but it seems the empirical results derived from previous studies are inconclusive because of the area of the study, the sectors studied, the time frame for the study and the measurement of the variables. In the area of the study, several studies in this area were conducted in foreign countries other than Nigeria.

Studies in this area of interest conducted internationally with the use of essential variables of accounting information such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share were mostly in quoted consumer and industrial goods companies. In Nigeria limited studies were conducted in this area of interest in accordance with the key variables of accounting information such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share and

earnings per share. The time frame mostly used in the previous studies are the combination of pre-adoption and post-adoption periods of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs). In this study, the panel linear regression technique will be employed with the inclusion of a control variable of asset turnover ratio (ATR) to achieve unique and different empirical results from previous studies in the extant literature.

The measures of market value in previous studies are mostly the adoption of Tobin's Q technique and price-to-book ratio. In this study, quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria were studied comparatively. The post adoption period of IFRSs was strictly considered from 2013 to 2024. The market value in this study was represented by share price. Variables such as net assets per share, net cash flows per share and earnings per share were rarely used in the previous studies in Nigeria which has to do with the influence of accounting information on market value of companies. Thus, the comparative analysis of influence of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria from the period of 2013 to 2024 would contribute to the extant literature and add to the stock of knowledge. Hence, the need for the study.

3. Methodology

The *ex-post facto* research design technique was employed because the study required secondary data collected from financial statements of the sampled quoted consumer and industrial goods

companies in Nigeria. In accordance with the view Kothari and Garg (2014), an empirical study that requires secondary data is one whose relevant data have been published or presented in recognized bulletins and which a researcher could retrieve at any time. Thus, the adoption of this research design enabled the researcher to examine the comparative influence of variables of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

The population of the study was made up of the aggregate quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria whose stocks were traded on the stock market of Nigeria regarded as Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group Plc. The quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria as at 31st December, 2025 were thirty-one (31) considered as the population. The thirty-one (31) quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria as at 31st December, 2025 were made up of twenty-one (21) quoted companies from consumer goods sector and ten (10) quoted companies from industrial goods sector. Thus, the population of this study was thirty-one (31) quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria and these were presented in Appendix One (i).

The sample size of this study was drawn from the population of twenty-one (21) and ten (10) quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria on the floor of NGX Group Plc. The sample size of twenty-three (23) quoted companies in Nigeria was made up of fifteen (15) companies drawn from consumer goods sector

and eight (8) companies drawn from industrial goods sector. The quoted consumer and industrial goods companies used as the sample size were those with available data for the essential variables of this study and for the period chosen as well.

The purposive sampling technique was adopted in this study. This was to enable the researcher to draw an appropriate sample size for the study by considering a suitable technique of selection (Kothari and Garg, 2014). In drawing the sample size, only those companies operating as single entities as well as the possibility of the researcher being able to retrieve the financial statements for the extraction of applicable data in line with the respective variables of this study. The sampled entities were presented in Appendix One (i).

The data for the study were collected from the financial statements of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria sampled for this study. The type of secondary data used were panel data obtained from the year 2013 to 2024. The nature of the data and with the objectives of the study necessitated the adoption of panel linear regression approach to establish the influence. The relevant data for the study were collected from the available financial statements of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria already prepared and published by management of the entities on the individual company's website and on the floor of Nigerian Exchange (NGX) Group (Kothari and Garg, 2014).

The key variables of this study regarded as variable description are broadly classified into

two and these are accounting information (AI) and market value (MV). Market Value (MV) is measured by Share Price (SP) while accounting information (AIF) is decomposed into sub-variables such as Net Assets Per Share (NAPS), Net Cash Flows Per Share (NCFPS) and Earnings Per Share (EPS). Asset Turnover Ratio (ATR) and Equity to Assets Ratio (EAR) were chosen as control variables of this study. The adapted empirical models were stated appropriately in line with the variables in each of the objectives of this study:

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NAPS_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.1a)

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NCFPS_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.2a)

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EPS_{ij} + e_t$$

Equation (3.3a)

The formulated models with the inclusion of control variables were stated accordingly:

Result (Expected Output)

These were presented on Table 3.1:

Table 3.1: Variable Description

S/N	Variable	Abbr.	Measurement	Apriori Expectation
1.	Share Price	SP	Share price is measured as the closing stock price per share of a quoted company.	
2.	Net Assets Per Share	NAPS	Net assets per share is measured as total assets less current liabilities divided by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company.	+

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NAPS_{ij} + \beta_2 ATR_{ij} + \beta_3 EAR + e_t$$

Equation (3.1b)

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 NCFPS_{ij} + \beta_2 ATR_{ij} + \beta_3 EAR + e_t$$

Equation (3.2b)

$$SP_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EPS_{ij} + \beta_2 ATR_{ij} + \beta_3 EAR + e_t$$

Equation (3.3b)

where: i=Number of companies; j=Number of years and e_t = Error terms.

The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential analytical tools. The descriptive statistics was used to examine the nature of the data relating to both accounting information and market value for the two sectors while the inferential statistics was used to establish the influence of variables accounting information on market value measured by share price. The various statistical tools of the regression to be used were R^2 , Adjusted R^2 , t-Statistic (t-Stat), Durbin-Watson (DW) Statistic, P-value and F-ratio. All tests were conducted based on 5% level of significance.

3.	Net Cash Flows Per Share	NCFPS	Net cash flows per share is measured as the aggregate of net cash flows from operating, investing and financing activities divided by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company.	+
4.	Earnings Per Share	EPS	Earnings per share is measured as the total profits for the year after corporation taxes divided by equity shares outstanding of a quoted company.	+
5.	Asset Turnover Ratio (Control Variable)	ATR	Asset turnover ratio is measured as total revenue divided by total assets of a quoted company.	+
6.	Equity to Assets Ratio (Control Variable)	EAR	Equity to assets ratio is measured as total equity reported divided by total assets of a quoted company.	+

Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

4. Results and Discussions

The data collected in accordance with the variables of interest were analysed appropriately

Table 4.1a: Descriptive Statistics for Consumer Goods Companies

	SP	NAPS	NCFPS	EPS	ATR	EAR
Mean	106.2898	27.13375	13.73877	0.829868	93.53614	37.30724
Median	18.57500	11.38700	3.280332	0.700579	89.72453	39.19723
Maximum	1556.500	576.8852	325.0215	61.77394	473.1307	100.0000
Minimum	0.860000	-8.630261	-61.86322	-207.6462	3.765040	-50.43258
Std. Dev.	305.5075	56.60101	41.35605	20.67774	51.75416	21.66665
Skewness	3.722444	6.771555	4.203326	-5.841131	3.253516	-0.466411
Kurtosis	15.77825	58.81480	25.20218	62.83095	22.38359	4.632777

for the purpose of deriving the empirical result for this study.

4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Jarque-Bera	1640.326	24740.31	4227.064	27871.64	3135.487	26.52090
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000002
Sum	19132.17	4884.075	2472.979	149.3762	16836.50	6715.302
Sum Sq. Dev.	16706937	573457.8	306147.7	76534.85	479450.3	84030.43
Observations	180	180	180	180	180	180

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table 4.1b: Descriptive Statistics for Industrial Goods Companies

	SP	NAPS	NCFPS	EPS	ATR	EAR
Mean	56.84719	30.02606	10.01276	5.134350	81.62519	54.90558
Median	20.50000	12.61906	3.628935	2.086404	61.27585	56.24028
Maximum	763.0000	204.3510	101.2200	60.87573	226.8053	95.89967
Minimum	0.460000	-88.95561	-45.31451	-2.371621	9.011359	16.02192
Std. Dev.	103.5548	40.86911	19.71619	8.777351	50.81000	15.18762
Skewness	4.076248	1.480276	1.678443	3.481820	0.933678	-0.278898
Kurtosis	24.93069	6.955944	9.351370	19.25090	2.952032	3.573337
Jarque-Bera	2189.674	97.65742	206.4343	1250.337	13.95728	2.559411
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000932	0.278119
Sum	5457.330	2882.502	961.2245	492.8976	7836.018	5270.936
Sum Sq. Dev.	1018743.	158677.0	36929.16	7318.979	245257.3	21913.07
Observations	96	96	96	96	96	96

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

The descriptive statistics for all the variables for the two sectors were presented on Table 4.1a and Table 4.1b.

4.2 Regression Analysis

Table 4.2a: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:22				
Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 180				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.

The linear regression analysis was performed in accordance with the objectives of this study comparatively using pooled panel regression approach.

C	0.438779	47.88626	0.009163	0.9927
NAPS	3.078377	0.330906	9.302866	0.0000
ATR	0.796631	0.351528	2.266197	0.0247
EAR	-1.398942	0.865750	-1.615874	0.1079
R-squared	0.395406	Mean dependent var		106.2898
Adjusted R-squared	0.385100	S.D. dependent var		305.5075
S.E. of regression	239.5654	Akaike info criterion		13.81750
Sum squared resid	10100918	Schwarz criterion		13.88846
Log likelihood	-1239.575	Hannan-Quinn criter.		13.84627
F-statistic	38.36811	Durbin-Watson stat		0.242243
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table 4.2b: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:40				
Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 8				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 96				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	48.46754	40.50158	1.196683	0.2345
NAPS	1.530286	0.229810	6.658914	0.0000
ATR	-0.146032	0.189074	-0.772356	0.4419
EAR	-0.467145	0.579666	-0.805887	0.4224
R-squared	0.393460	Mean dependent var		56.84719
Adjusted R-squared	0.373681	S.D. dependent var		103.5548
S.E. of regression	81.95363	Akaike info criterion		11.69096
Sum squared resid	617908.6	Schwarz criterion		11.79781
Log likelihood	-557.1660	Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.73415
F-statistic	19.89330	Durbin-Watson stat		1.132539
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

From Table 4.2a and 4.2b, comparatively, it was observed that Net Asset Per Share (NAPS) exerted positive and significant influence on Market Value (SP) for both quoted consumer

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA And Anietie Sunday DAVID, Msc

goods and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. With the coefficient of NAPS, it could be said that in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, NAPS exerted higher influence on SP than in quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Also, by comparing the significance of the two models using F-statistics, it was observed that quoted consumer goods had a better model than that quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria for the fact that the

computed F-statistics of the quoted consumer goods companies was higher than that of quoted industrial goods companies. For the influence of the predictor of NAPS on SP of the companies from the two sectors, it was observed that the study was not in line with Innocent *et al.* (2020) who examined accounting information and stock prices of quoted manufacturing firms: Multi-variant panel data evidence from Nigeria.

Table 4.3a: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:27				
Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 180				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	53.68478	43.57924	1.231889	0.2196
NCFPS	4.674728	0.422170	11.07308	0.0000
ATR	0.535169	0.332721	1.608462	0.1095
EAR	-1.653235	0.800182	-2.066073	0.0403
R-squared	0.468435	Mean dependent var		106.2898
Adjusted R-squared	0.459375	S.D. dependent var		305.5075
S.E. of regression	224.6312	Akaike info criterion		13.68877
Sum squared resid	8880817.	Schwarz criterion		13.75972
Log likelihood	-1227.989	Hannan-Quinn criter.		13.71754
F-statistic	51.69934	Durbin-Watson stat		0.885117
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table 4.3b: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:45				

Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 8				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 96				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	57.67614	39.02021	1.478109	0.1428
NCFPS	3.083534	0.428718	7.192455	0.0000
ATR	-0.355813	0.173371	-2.052329	0.0430
EAR	-0.048452	0.562749	-0.086099	0.9316
R-squared	0.424646	Mean dependent var		56.84719
Adjusted R-squared	0.405885	S.D. dependent var		103.5548
S.E. of regression	79.81892	Akaike info criterion		11.63817
Sum squared resid	586137.5	Schwarz criterion		11.74502
Log likelihood	-554.6322	Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.68136
F-statistic	22.63387	Durbin-Watson stat		1.531920
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

From Table 4.3a and 4.3b, comparatively, it was observed that Net Cash Flow Per Share (NCFPS) exerted positive and significant influence on Market Value (SP) for both quoted consumer goods and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. With the coefficient of NCFPS, it could be said that in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, NCFPS exerted higher influence on SP than in quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Also, by comparing the significance of the two models using F-statistics, it was observed that quoted consumer goods had

a better model than that quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria for the fact that the computed F-statistics of the quoted consumer goods companies was higher than that of quoted industrial goods companies. For the influence of the predictor of NCFPS on SP of the companies from the two sectors, it was observed that the study was in line with Nwaobia *et al.* (2016) who examined value relevance of accounting information and firm value: A study of consumer goods manufacturing sector in Nigeria.

Table 4.4a: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:32				
Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, Phd, ACA And Anietie Sunday DAVID, Msc

Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 180				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	151.1119	55.14784	2.740124	0.0068
EPS	3.348210	1.046906	3.198196	0.0016
ATR	1.155008	0.414388	2.787260	0.0059
EAR	-4.171727	1.002164	-4.162719	0.0000
R-squared	0.147648	Mean dependent var		106.2898
Adjusted R-squared	0.133119	S.D. dependent var		305.5075
S.E. of regression	284.4471	Akaike info criterion		14.16094
Sum squared resid	14240190	Schwarz criterion		14.23190
Log likelihood	-1270.485	Hannan-Quinn criter.		14.18971
F-statistic	10.16249	Durbin-Watson stat		0.173044
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000003			

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table 4.4b: Pooled Panel Linear Regression Output

Dependent Variable: SP				
Method: Panel Least Squares				
Date: 01/27/26 Time: 14:49				
Sample: 2013 2024				
Periods included: 12				
Cross-sections included: 8				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 96				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	50.33514	31.62167	1.591793	0.1149
EPS	8.930620	0.799910	11.16452	0.0000
ATR	-0.206234	0.142853	-1.443683	0.1522
EAR	-0.409922	0.458856	-0.893356	0.3740
R-squared	0.618289	Mean dependent var		56.84719
Adjusted R-squared	0.605842	S.D. dependent var		103.5548
S.E. of regression	65.01383	Akaike info criterion		11.22785
Sum squared resid	388865.4	Schwarz criterion		11.33470
Log likelihood	-534.9368	Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.27104
F-statistic	49.67332	Durbin-Watson stat		2.052172
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, Phd, ACA And Anietie Sunday DAVID, Msc

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

From Table 4.4a and 4.4b, comparatively, it was observed that Earnings Per Share (EPS) exerted positive and significant influence on Market Value (SP) for both quoted consumer goods and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. With the coefficient of EPS, it could be said that in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria, EPS exerted lower influence on SP than in quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Also, by comparing the significance of the two models using F-statistics, it was observed that quoted industrial goods had a better model than that quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria for the fact that the computed F-statistics of the quoted industrial goods companies was higher than that of quoted consumer goods companies. For the influence of the predictor of EPS on SP of the companies from the two sectors, it was observed that the study was not in line with Etim *et al.* (2022) who assessed value relevance of accounting information and share prices movement of quoted consumer and industrial goods in Nigeria.

5. Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

The study was conducted to comparatively ascertain the influence of accounting information on market value of quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Fifteen (15) and eight (8) quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria were sampled for the study respectively. Pooled panel regression approach was adopted to establish the influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable. The

dependent variable of the study was market value while the independent variable was accounting information. The key variables in the study were share price (SP), net assets per share (NAPS), net cash flows per share (NCFPS) and earnings per share (EPS). Asset turnover ratio (ATR) and equity to asset ratio (EAR) were used as control variables.

From the analysis of the study, it was concluded that all the predictors of accounting information exerted positive and significant influence on market value of both quoted consumer and industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Comparatively, it was ascertained that accounting information exerted more influence on market value of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria than industrial goods companies in Nigeria as NAPS and NCFPS represented accounting information. On the other hand, accounting information exerted more influence on market value of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria than quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria comparatively as EPS represented accounting information.

However, from the findings, the following recommendations were suggested:

- i. Investment in acquisition of non-current assets should be made more in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria than industrial goods companies in Nigeria in order raise net assets per share and influence positively on market value.
- ii. Stringent cash policy should be adopted in consumer goods companies in Nigeria than

the industrial goods companies for the purpose of raising net cash flows per share and maximizing market value.

iii. The managers of quoted industrial goods companies in Nigeria should effectively and efficiently manage their operating cost and expenses to realise more profit after tax (PAT) for the purpose of raising the value of earnings per share.

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APPENDIX ONE (i)

Table 3.1: Population of the Study

S/N	Company	Sector
1.	Cadbury Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
2.	Champion Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
3.	Dangote Sugar Ref. Plc	Consumer Goods
4.	DN Tyre and Rubber Plc	Consumer Goods
5.	Flour Mills Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
6.	Golden Guinea Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
7.	Guinness Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
8.	Honeywell Flour Mills Plc	Consumer Goods
9.	International Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
10.	Menichols Plc	Consumer Goods
11.	Multi-Trex Int. Foods Plc	Consumer Goods
12.	N Nig. Flour Mills Plc	Consumer Goods
13.	Nascon Allied Indust. Plc	Consumer Goods
14.	Nestle Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
15.	Nigerian Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
16.	Nigerian Enamelware Plc	Consumer Goods
17.	P Z Cussons Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
18.	Unilever Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
19.	Union Dicon Salt Plc	Consumer Goods
20.	Vitafoam Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
21.	BUA Food Plc	Consumer Goods

22.	Austin Laz and Co. Plc	Industrial Goods
23.	Berger Paints Plc	Industrial Goods
24.	Beta Glass Plc	Industrial Goods
25.	CAP Plc	Industrial Goods
26.	BUA Cement Plc	Industrial Goods
27.	Cutix Plc	Industrial Goods
28.	Dangote Cement Plc	Industrial Goods
29.	Lafarge Africa Plc	Industrial Goods
30.	Meyer Plc	Industrial Goods
31.	Notore Chemical Indust. Plc	Industrial Goods

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2026)

Table 3.2: Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Company	Sector
1.	Cadbury Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
2.	Champion Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
3.	Dangote Sugar Ref. Plc	Consumer Goods
4.	Flour Mills Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
5.	Guinness Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
6.	Honeywell Flour Mills Plc	Consumer Goods
7.	International Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
8.	N Nig. Flour Mills Plc	Consumer Goods
9.	Nascon Allied Indust. Plc	Consumer Goods
10.	Nestle Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
11.	Nigerian Brew. Plc	Consumer Goods
12.	Nigerian Enamelware Plc	Consumer Goods
13.	P Z Cussons Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
14.	Unilever Nigeria Plc	Consumer Goods
15.	Vitafoam Nig. Plc	Consumer Goods
16.	Berger Paints Plc	Industrial Goods
17.	Beta Glass Plc	Industrial Goods
18.	BUA Cement Plc	Industrial Goods
19.	Cutix Plc	Industrial Goods
20.	Dangote Cement Plc	Industrial Goods
21.	Lafarge Africa Plc	Industrial Goods
22.	Meyer Plc	Industrial Goods

23.	CAP Plc	Industrial Goods
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Source: Researcher’s Compilation (2026)

APPENDIX TWO (ii)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	91.94	9.20	4.07	1.92	82.83	55.58
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	40.00	4.72	5.40	0.48	105.89	40.05
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	17.15	8.93	4.18	0.61	97.92	43.23
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	10.29	8.29	0.34	-0.16	105.59	38.94
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	15.67	8.46	-0.41	0.16	116.38	41.31
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	10.00	9.29	5.32	0.44	130.68	46.05
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	10.55	10.06	2.25	0.57	136.54	47.10
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	9.00	9.98	0.99	0.50	106.61	40.80
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	8.80	11.53	-2.82	0.24	96.99	31.21
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	11.50	12.05	-7.74	0.31	92.46	22.28
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	17.30	3.87	7.30	-10.16	105.13	8.52
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2024	23.00	2.28	16.77	-9.75	178.30	6.04
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	70.25	58.40	-4.13	3.73	100.78	39.07
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	61.81	57.95	19.91	4.39	111.61	40.74
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	33.50	43.98	11.74	0.92	99.24	41.74
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	19.40	45.27	-0.41	3.97	106.25	42.97
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	17.98	48.21	-3.10	3.75	109.10	31.44
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	37.30	44.52	-13.61	2.25	120.70	46.94
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	18.00	42.86	-0.40	4.71	117.88	44.24
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2020	21.25	52.10	33.96	3.07	125.65	46.56
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2021	28.80	62.25	1.97	4.92	140.90	42.04
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2022	31.05	67.07	3.02	5.32	170.79	35.82
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2023	31.00	67.16	-14.79	3.46	128.32	25.28
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2024	30.50	79.59	-11.59	4.10	129.09	18.43
Guinness Nig. Plc	2013	251.71	46.34	32.54	-3.42	101.16	100.00
Guinness Nig. Plc	2014	189.21	58.49	24.00	-1.40	82.52	100.00
Guinness Nig. Plc	2015	162.81	50.57	41.41	5.18	96.93	39.54
Guinness Nig. Plc	2016	103.40	46.41	-0.81	-1.34	74.44	30.41
Guinness Nig. Plc	2017	67.95	54.66	24.51	1.28	86.22	29.41

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA and Anietie Sunday DAVID, MSc

Guinness Nig. Plc	2018	97.75	50.41	5.87	3.07	93.29	57.15
Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	47.65	51.10	16.42	2.50	81.78	55.39
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	14.50	38.14	10.95	-5.74	72.41	50.67
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	29.00	39.47	33.80	0.57	94.69	43.85
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	90.50	46.53	10.46	7.15	95.90	41.72
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	59.95	26.51	22.64	-8.29	94.91	23.34
Guinness Nig. Plc	2024	61.90	1.57	95.95	-25.00	132.44	0.96

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	2.94	3.52	-0.37	0.36	82.45	33.47
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	3.87	4.51	0.70	0.42	86.30	32.28
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	3.00	4.55	2.26	0.14	72.20	29.90
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	1.46	4.01	1.09	0.38	66.91	21.52
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	1.05	10.95	0.45	0.54	47.04	46.25
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	2.55	12.18	3.68	0.56	57.26	45.17
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	1.20	12.01	1.92	0.01	54.11	41.21
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	0.98	11.18	1.18	0.08	56.55	40.27
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	1.18	10.78	1.87	0.14	74.35	39.33
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	3.50	10.43	-0.50	-0.12	91.03	37.65
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	3.13	9.44	-0.32	0.03	89.30	19.99
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2024	3.15	7.59	18.22	-1.28	126.41	15.34
Int Breweries Plc	2013	20.95	4.65	-2.70	0.71	75.48	40.72
Int Breweries Plc	2014	24.20	5.39	4.00	0.64	75.89	46.24
Int Breweries Plc	2015	18.90	6.13	1.77	0.73	68.44	40.33
Int Breweries Plc	2016	20.49	5.32	4.72	0.90	69.50	41.81
Int Breweries Plc	2017	54.50	7.46	11.45	0.16	15.73	16.90
Int Breweries Plc	2018	30.50	22.27	-7.27	0.45	38.87	11.33
Int Breweries Plc	2019	9.50	18.73	4.72	-3.23	36.25	2.04
Int Breweries Plc	2020	5.95	5.76	3.18	-0.46	36.71	40.72
Int Breweries Plc	2021	4.95	5.37	3.28	-0.66	38.79	28.79

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA and Anietie Sunday DAVID, MSc

Int Breweries Plc	2022	4.70	10.18	4.32	-0.81	45.15	24.23
Int Breweries Plc	2023	4.94	19.22	5.82	-2.21	36.05	16.99
Int Breweries Plc	2024	5.50	14.50	9.83	-3.49	67.18	61.67
N Nig. Flour Plc	2013	23.80	11.16	7.85	1.26	322.95	44.31
N Nig. Flour Plc	2014	22.05	11.67	-0.06	1.31	348.74	54.30
N Nig. Flour Plc	2015	17.15	1.03	0.37	-0.11	473.13	66.51
N Nig. Flour Plc	2016	6.65	2.26	-0.64	-0.25	53.12	67.87
N Nig. Flour Plc	2017	6.31	7.62	-10.24	-0.10	30.68	28.58
N Nig. Flour Plc	2018	6.55	14.27	-3.50	-0.34	48.36	19.84
N Nig. Flour Plc	2019	4.30	11.83	14.45	-0.18	83.12	23.05
N Nig. Flour Plc	2020	4.30	20.81	325.02	0.36	104.11	32.61
N Nig. Flour Plc	2021	6.20	19.82	6.69	0.39	117.68	37.85
N Nig. Flour Plc	2022	9.00	19.77	23.02	0.45	114.40	21.44
N Nig. Flour Plc	2023	11.95	42.83	9.28	1.53	90.66	36.91
N Nig. Flour Plc	2024	48.30	51.39	11.78	8.56	128.05	45.07

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	14.99	2.88	2.51	1.02	94.80	60.30
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	6.22	2.72	3.28	0.70	89.60	50.23
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	7.15	3.15	2.40	0.79	99.28	-8.13
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	8.50	3.58	1.71	0.91	74.35	9.82
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	18.50	5.10	7.81	0.97	89.85	-6.16
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	18.00	5.35	3.37	0.77	85.13	-13.13
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	12.95	7.52	4.19	0.70	71.09	28.68
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	14.50	7.09	6.45	1.02	63.22	28.71
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	13.20	7.66	2.10	1.12	82.13	36.11
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	11.00	9.45	0.39	2.07	105.86	34.29
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	60.39	12.81	10.29	5.18	96.69	32.86
Nascon Allied Plc	2024	38.00	19.30	3.31	5.77	153.35	54.85
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	1,200.00	95.11	76.36	28.08	122.99	21.26
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	1,011.75	78.17	73.47	28.05	135.14	28.34
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	860.00	75.04	87.80	29.95	126.89	31.88
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	810.00	61.25	106.47	10.00	107.27	18.21

Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	1,555.99	84.68	98.71	42.55	166.31	30.57
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	1,485.00	88.58	184.56	54.26	164.03	30.94
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	1,469.90	85.58	138.80	57.63	146.88	23.56
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	1,505.00	101.12	176.54	49.47	116.61	11.90
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	1,556.50	144.73	113.98	50.51	113.40	6.89
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	963.90	248.08	-32.56	61.77	107.66	7.30
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	1,090.00	367.29	147.00	100.26	94.04	-13.41
Nestle Nig. Plc	2024	975.00	576.89	200.92	207.65	111.66	-10.75
Nig. Breweries Plc	2013	134.32	32.98	25.17	5.70	76.82	32.13
Nig. Breweries Plc	2014	132.24	31.03	16.63	5.62	76.27	49.24
Nig. Breweries Plc	2015	108.80	27.25	20.80	4.80	82.39	48.28
Nig. Breweries Plc	2016	118.39	28.10	14.51	3.58	85.34	45.10
Nig. Breweries Plc	2017	107.92	28.26	17.52	4.13	95.58	46.55
Nig. Breweries Plc	2018	68.40	31.06	7.90	2.43	90.09	42.86
Nig. Breweries Plc	2019	47.20	30.39	10.52	2.01	84.44	43.81
Nig. Breweries Plc	2020	44.80	29.43	17.69	0.94	75.83	36.26
Nig. Breweries Plc	2021	40.00	26.66	24.42	1.62	90.58	35.67
Nig. Breweries Plc	2022	41.00	72.67	4.96	1.74	88.60	29.11
Nig. Breweries Plc	2023	37.00	26.68	4.97	-13.23	75.19	8.17
Nig. Breweries Plc	2024	32.00	16.63	-0.91	-4.66	95.44	41.33

Source: Researcher's Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2013	26.89	23.98	0.78	1.17	114.19	53.73
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2014	26.89	24.67	-9.23	1.36	83.32	40.26
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2015	26.52	25.52	-24.66	1.17	51.93	25.99
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2016	24.82	26.93	21.57	2.11	61.57	31.16
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2017	24.44	27.03	-9.90	0.71	43.39	24.49
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2018	22.10	21.98	39.71	-0.04	36.08	31.11
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2019	22.10	18.84	9.34	-3.18	16.89	26.98
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2020	22.10	14.31	12.98	-4.61	9.98	16.67
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2021	19.90	10.50	0.96	-3.62	6.44	12.03

Nig. Enamelware Plc	2022	16.20	4.91	-0.48	-5.67	8.05	3.28
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2023	17.75	25.36	-61.86	22.18	3.77	30.33
Nig. Enamelware Plc	2024	19.30	-8.63	-13.63	-34.17	28.74	-29.78
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2013	50.98	12.82	3.31	1.34	98.68	64.23
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2014	36.00	11.84	4.86	1.28	102.73	59.94
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2015	29.18	7.64	2.42	0.55	152.01	55.26
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2016	20.61	9.55	3.96	0.10	123.58	60.06
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2017	18.36	9.58	3.45	0.56	74.98	46.65
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2018	20.85	9.42	4.61	0.41	78.42	45.26
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2019	8.10	9.58	-1.70	0.15	73.39	52.58
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2020	5.50	7.77	2.05	1.50	65.46	40.17
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2021	5.50	7.44	4.76	0.21	68.95	33.22
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2022	11.45	7.37	-3.94	0.45	72.94	29.89
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2023	16.90	7.22	-3.91	2.15	60.84	25.88
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2024	22.00	11.01	13.53	-11.48	76.88	-14.18
Unilever Nig. Plc	2013	53.80	4.14	5.35	1.25	137.14	21.36
Unilever Nig. Plc	2014	35.80	3.67	-0.11	0.64	121.90	16.35
Unilever Nig. Plc	2015	41.15	4.09	6.36	0.32	118.04	15.95
Unilever Nig. Plc	2016	35.05	5.02	-0.69	0.81	96.26	16.13
Unilever Nig. Plc	2017	41.00	14.69	-5.39	1.30	70.36	62.69
Unilever Nig. Plc	2018	37.00	15.44	1.27	1.84	70.46	62.79
Unilever Nig. Plc	2019	22.00	11.99	-0.24	-1.29	58.34	64.17
Unilever Nig. Plc	2020	13.90	11.09	0.64	-0.69	67.70	67.89
Unilever Nig. Plc	2021	14.50	11.85	3.72	0.59	65.13	60.73
Unilever Nig. Plc	2022	11.60	12.19	2.30	0.78	70.64	53.88
Unilever Nig. Plc	2023	18.65	14.36	0.51	1.47	89.32	64.07
Unilever Nig. Plc	2024	38.00	15.80	4.24	2.64	105.56	60.08

Source: Researcher's Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Champion B. Plc	2013	16.91	-5.05	2.21	-1.31	24.44	-50.43
Champion B. Plc	2014	6.98	0.84	0.22	-0.10	34.43	61.20
Champion B. Plc	2015	3.38	0.93	0.25	0.01	33.90	68.95
Champion B. Plc	2016	2.45	0.99	0.10	0.07	38.80	77.01

Champion B. Plc	2017	2.08	1.08	0.12	0.07	47.35	80.64
Champion B. Plc	2018	1.99	1.04	0.31	-0.03	45.43	75.67
Champion B. Plc	2019	0.95	1.08	0.35	0.02	63.08	73.14
Champion B. Plc	2020	0.86	1.16	0.46	0.02	62.03	70.75
Champion B. Plc	2021	2.35	1.28	0.72	0.13	77.99	68.36
Champion B. Plc	2022	5.50	1.60	0.66	0.20	79.52	71.95
Champion B. Plc	2023	3.09	1.60	1.45	0.05	61.87	54.52
Champion B. Plc	2024	3.95	1.36	0.95	0.09	97.87	56.48
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	11.70	5.07	-0.51	1.13	117.63	65.58
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	6.35	5.34	-0.03	0.99	96.73	52.85
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	6.03	5.23	1.54	1.05	102.88	60.16
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	5.90	5.93	3.76	1.18	156.94	62.24
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	20.00	8.87	3.79	3.15	100.03	50.09
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	15.25	9.37	0.88	2.15	82.09	60.04
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	13.60	9.35	0.90	1.07	45.01	61.18
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	17.60	11.24	5.51	2.58	79.59	48.33
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	17.40	11.70	12.77	1.87	79.01	37.16
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2022	16.05	15.30	11.96	4.47	82.13	35.04
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2023	67.90	6.76	2.78	-5.93	73.45	13.61
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2024	36.00	18.08	-47.04	-15.71	65.37	17.65
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	2.78	10.17	5.72	1.37	165.52	34.85
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2014	2.98	10.67	7.23	0.96	140.68	33.96
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2015	4.92	5.07	1.35	0.20	129.15	32.41
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2016	2.39	5.11	-2.58	0.40	93.06	33.40
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2017	2.09	5.14	3.91	0.18	122.71	34.40
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2018	2.92	6.98	-1.55	0.47	116.20	31.82
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2019	3.90	6.31	7.10	1.26	164.50	48.00
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2020	6.00	9.71	3.13	2.76	108.68	43.87
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2021	17.10	11.56	-2.65	3.51	107.79	41.76
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2022	20.95	13.35	-0.10	3.53	114.13	40.67
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2023	22.45	14.07	-2.10	2.73	102.25	34.66
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2024	22.00	21.75	15.14	-0.72	160.09	47.11

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Berger Paints Plc	2013	8.00	9.76	-2.49	0.89	74.73	68.26
Berger Paints Plc	2014	8.55	9.74	-0.72	0.51	84.69	67.58
Berger Paints Plc	2015	10.00	9.50	2.94	1.14	77.58	66.41
Berger Paints Plc	2016	6.40	9.65	5.63	0.77	63.45	63.48
Berger Paints Plc	2017	8.48	11.15	1.26	0.85	69.88	61.26
Berger Paints Plc	2018	8.60	11.21	3.65	1.11	74.47	62.03
Berger Paints Plc	2019	6.75	12.35	3.40	1.55	70.76	60.66
Berger Paints Plc	2020	7.35	12.57	2.65	0.50	77.19	63.30
Berger Paints Plc	2021	8.55	12.67	2.31	0.47	97.15	63.21
Berger Paints Plc	2022	6.00	13.24	2.98	0.72	114.53	60.11
Berger Paints Plc	2023	17.35	15.71	1.77	1.62	119.65	53.42
Berger Paints Plc	2024	21.00	16.22	3.61	2.12	142.53	51.17
Beta Glass Plc	2013	12.02	35.49	9.69	2.95	51.89	50.63
Beta Glass Plc	2014	23.15	38.51	15.44	4.78	61.77	59.24
Beta Glass Plc	2015	44.54	43.29	17.71	3.98	58.71	64.69
Beta Glass Plc	2016	25.27	52.39	11.60	7.60	57.53	64.71
Beta Glass Plc	2017	42.76	58.34	6.63	8.23	58.06	65.80
Beta Glass Plc	2018	56.92	64.72	31.08	10.11	57.12	64.30
Beta Glass Plc	2019	44.83	74.10	19.83	11.16	56.47	66.36
Beta Glass Plc	2020	46.17	78.31	11.54	6.93	47.51	68.92
Beta Glass Plc	2021	44.12	91.43	20.93	10.92	58.60	66.75
Beta Glass Plc	2022	39.60	83.01	4.07	7.81	71.55	60.92
Beta Glass Plc	2023	59.40	172.20	34.29	10.74	58.87	48.67
Beta Glass Plc	2024	71.50	120.69	84.35	22.71	85.60	47.17
BUA Cement Plc	2013	11.75	8.72	2.92	1.24	101.68	55.02
BUA Cement Plc	2014	10.35	9.77	3.11	1.53	95.81	59.86
BUA Cement Plc	2015	9.35	10.35	3.67	0.96	76.04	59.16
BUA Cement Plc	2016	4.76	11.56	3.29	1.00	70.33	57.38
BUA Cement Plc	2017	9.50	13.91	5.24	2.57	79.47	58.47
BUA Cement Plc	2018	19.40	25.58	0.32	0.44	9.12	95.90
BUA Cement Plc	2019	18.10	26.12	1.36	0.55	9.01	95.52
BUA Cement Plc	2020	77.35	16.48	-45.31	2.14	27.33	49.06
BUA Cement Plc	2021	67.05	17.22	13.92	2.66	35.32	54.65

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA and Anietie Sunday DAVID, MSc

BUA Cement Plc	2022	97.75	25.05	9.26	2.98	41.30	47.04
BUA Cement Plc	2023	185.00	24.76	7.27	2.05	37.84	31.69
BUA Cement Plc	2024	93.00	29.41	30.97	2.18	55.81	24.74

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Cutix Plc	2013	1.46	0.77	0.42	0.17	179.68	55.65
Cutix Plc	2014	1.90	1.19	0.90	0.24	128.10	40.11
Cutix Plc	2015	1.82	1.19	0.52	0.17	119.79	37.77
Cutix Plc	2016	1.39	1.29	1.40	0.22	149.91	46.00
Cutix Plc	2017	0.89	1.38	0.39	0.29	157.77	43.52
Cutix Plc	2018	2.95	1.68	1.40	0.50	178.31	45.81
Cutix Plc	2019	1.85	0.52	0.24	0.14	189.91	56.38
Cutix Plc	2020	0.61	0.66	0.04	0.11	138.52	49.77
Cutix Plc	2021	1.11	0.71	0.18	0.17	140.49	46.12
Cutix Plc	2022	2.44	0.85	0.68	0.22	154.38	54.40
Cutix Plc	2023	2.25	0.98	0.29	0.22	159.14	55.77
Cutix Plc	2024	3.10	1.29	0.52	0.31	168.69	53.79
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	218.99	39.36	30.88	12.34	45.22	69.56
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	200.00	44.46	25.96	10.90	38.56	66.28
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	170.00	57.74	29.16	12.51	34.61	66.56
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	173.78	65.28	24.92	21.61	28.36	65.31
Dang. Cem. Plc	2017	230.00	74.36	32.80	14.94	34.29	61.51
Dang. Cem. Plc	2018	189.70	84.34	39.19	28.25	35.91	75.12
Dang. Cem. Plc	2019	142.00	82.95	42.26	15.34	33.46	70.30
Dang. Cem. Plc	2020	244.90	92.57	45.98	20.69	34.02	63.91
Dang. Cem. Plc	2021	257.00	102.37	62.00	22.37	38.47	56.60
Dang. Cem. Plc	2022	261.00	110.48	50.66	23.64	45.34	56.11
Dang. Cem. Plc	2023	763.00	114.04	38.70	28.77	42.26	52.21
Dang. Cem. Plc	2024	394.00	204.35	101.22	60.88	42.21	40.96
Lafarge Africa Plc	2013	115.00	40.16	19.83	9.34	60.78	57.95
Lafarge Africa Plc	2014	73.18	69.73	21.35	6.44	30.80	80.51

Lafarge Plc	Africa	2015	88.00	73.27	14.28	6.55	30.05	79.37
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2016	38.91	77.55	-9.02	3.79	16.22	63.26
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2017	43.60	59.85	-2.20	-2.37	28.75	42.97
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2018	12.45	46.56	10.55	0.48	32.38	44.27
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2019	15.30	25.51	7.63	1.41	37.68	72.27
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2020	21.05	23.64	5.14	1.78	40.08	74.01
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2021	23.95	24.84	-42.01	3.32	49.11	74.03
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2022	24.00	27.27	-3.76	3.42	55.92	71.29
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2023	36.00	-88.96	15.12	2.98	54.00	65.26
Lafarge Plc	Africa	2024	71.00	36.41	20.79	6.19	65.26	52.05

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

Table A: Computed Data for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	SP (₦)	NAPS (₦)	NCFPS (₦)	EPS (₦)	ATR (%)	EAR (%)
Meyer Paints Plc	2013	1.41	5.68	1.34	-0.08	57.75	23.96
Meyer Paints Plc	2014	0.91	5.37	1.14	-0.10	55.03	23.88
Meyer Paints Plc	2015	0.67	5.85	0.42	0.25	51.59	27.73
Meyer Paints Plc	2016	0.90	4.78	-0.14	-0.74	50.08	19.45
Meyer Paints Plc	2017	0.73	1.24	-0.11	-0.54	58.02	16.02
Meyer Paints Plc	2018	0.59	1.58	0.10	0.64	52.75	33.77
Meyer Paints Plc	2019	0.54	1.52	4.91	-0.03	29.73	16.33
Meyer Paints Plc	2020	0.50	3.37	-11.23	2.23	28.03	58.13
Meyer Paints Plc	2021	0.46	2.07	0.75	0.07	56.28	50.50
Meyer Paints Plc	2022	2.27	2.89	-0.48	0.79	75.22	73.22
Meyer Paints Plc	2023	3.56	3.35	0.03	0.47	93.48	67.34

Meyer Paints Plc	2024	9.25	3.67	0.01	0.59	111.05	63.23
CAP Plc	2013	48.45	1.93	3.87	2.02	204.14	41.78
CAP Plc	2014	38.00	1.79	4.36	2.37	226.81	38.32
CAP Plc	2015	37.60	2.25	1.64	2.49	206.99	44.59
CAP Plc	2016	30.55	3.46	0.96	2.29	138.61	46.45
CAP Plc	2017	34.60	3.35	4.46	2.14	141.88	44.72
CAP Plc	2018	34.85	4.19	5.02	2.90	121.53	44.51
CAP Plc	2019	24.00	3.85	5.04	2.49	124.40	37.30
CAP Plc	2020	20.00	5.35	0.76	1.75	104.11	43.92
CAP Plc	2021	19.45	5.81	0.79	1.42	117.27	36.40
CAP Plc	2022	17.80	8.51	1.83	2.92	143.28	49.23
CAP Plc	2023	24.00	10.39	7.28	3.09	155.40	51.84
CAP Plc	2024	47.00	14.44	9.88	4.67	184.79	54.05

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2026)

APPENDIX THREE (iii)

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2013	35,760,753.0	43,172,624.0	6,023,220.0	14,386,781.0	23,994,931.0	6,621,476.0	-2,977,964.0	-3,136,485.0	3,130,374.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2014	30,518,586.0	28,820,107.0	1,512,687.0	14,042,218.0	11,542,026.0	1,419,524.0	-1,129,439.0	-14,354,137.0	3,130,374.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2015	27,825,194.0	28,417,005.0	1,153,295.0	11,651,634.0	12,285,297.0	5,797,705.0	-787,360.0	-1,270,811.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2016	29,979,410.0	28,392,951.0	-296,402.0	12,820,278.0	11,056,734.0	-61,766.0	-221,081.0	-478,323.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2017	33,079,446.0	28,423,121.0	299,998.0	12,529,586.0	11,742,791.0	-1,471,632.0	-950,998.0	258,655.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2018	35,973,479.0	27,528,040.0	823,085.0	10,085,404.0	12,676,146.0	6,695,082.0	-722,841.0	-2,578,012.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2019	39,326,807.0	28,801,938.0	1,070,845.0	9,901,393.0	13,566,235.0	2,285,899.0	-1,515,541.0	-431,344.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2020	35,407,323.0	33,210,684.0	931,827.0	14,474,694.0	13,549,523.0	4,254,793.0	-845,019.0	3,246,691.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2021	42,372,034.0	43,688,291.0	449,712.0	22,024,707.0	13,636,354.0	674,014.0	-726,317.0	6,697,497.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2022	55,212,617.0	59,713,684.0	583,111.0	37,088,401.0	13,302,628.0	-2,534,928.0	-694,897.0	12,692,504.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2023	80,378,955.0	76,458,376.0	-19,089,704.0	69,193,515.0	6,513,678.0	2,797,230.0	-1,433,138.0	-9,473,254.0	1,878,202.0
Cadbury Nig. Plc	2024	129,165,095.0	72,443,944.0	-22,224,942.0	67,241,651.0	4,379,193.0	20,109,534.0	-4,498,234.0	-13,624,812.0	2,280,284.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2013	225,629,747.0	223,889,726.0	8,900,989.0	84,562,515.0	87,463,784.0	-527,216.0	-9,693,976.0	19,025,249.0	2,385,684.0

Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2014	245,701,366.0	220,145,554.0	10,465,518.0	81,893,576.0	89,678,463.0	9,934,541.0	-3,308,781.0	-34,249,281.0	2,385,684.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2015	229,777,869.0	231,529,878.0	2,419,544.0	116,115,447.0	96,651,666.0	10,096,781.0	-5,720,460.0	-14,990,590.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2016	247,876,504.0	233,296,607.0	10,425,786.0	114,508,685.0	100,244,139.0	20,924,187.0	23,900,756.0	-1,906,428.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2017	375,225,284.0	343,933,157.0	9,829,046.0	217,412,600.0	108,115,699.0	-14,328,877.0	-27,311,825.0	21,107,005.0	2,624,252.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2018	389,397,836.0	322,604,582.0	9,244,729.0	140,074,526.0	151,446,296.0	-24,037,585.0	54,158,200.0	-22,394,367.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2019	370,205,529.0	314,058,187.0	19,317,654.0	138,329,706.0	138,929,273.0	3,544,753.0	34,258,841.0	-29,077,558.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2020	394,884,217.0	314,267,060.0	12,582,571.0	100,624,270.0	146,316,890.0	72,239,224.0	-24,989,243.0	-42,011,798.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2021	535,881,585.0	380,322,525.0	20,172,489.0	125,066,314.0	159,878,794.0	10,478,062.0	-9,176,062.0	11,575,002.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2022	832,810,561.0	487,617,576.0	21,819,816.0	212,620,619.0	174,663,847.0	51,219.0	1,448,389.0	-13,795,610.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2023	923,015,713.0	719,285,322.0	14,173,904.0	443,900,217.0	181,820,527.0	-14,728,972.0	-14,137,836.0	60,038,437.0	4,100,394.0
Flour Mills Nig. Plc	2024	1,346,992,354.0	1,043,445,303.0	16,817,754.0	717,075,540.0	192,333,092.0	23,148,591.0	23,327,794.0	47,340,470.0	4,100,394.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	
Guinness Nig. Plc	2013	122,463,538.0	121,060,621.0	-5,145,149.0	51,275,097.0	121,060,621.0	24,298,136.0	-	14,081,901.0	-10,617,820.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2014	109,202,120.0	132,328,273.0	-2,108,080.0	44,248,749.0	132,328,273.0	19,157,202.0	-	13,683,695.0	-3,304,804.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2015	118,495,882.0	122,246,632.0	7,794,899.0	46,100,344.0	48,341,376.0	32,538,985.0	-	-8,454,576.0	-21,361,905.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2016	101,973,030.0	136,992,444.0	-2,015,886.0	67,109,622.0	41,660,605.0	-1,320,097.0	-	-8,532,239.0	8,425,931.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2017	125,919,817.0	146,038,216.0	1,923,720.0	63,719,662.0	42,943,015.0	18,045,541.0	-	-7,568,324.0	-11,294,243.0	1,505,888.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2018	142,975,792.0	153,254,968.0	6,717,605.0	42,847,115.0	87,588,174.0	10,589,789.0	-	15,629,117.0	13,366,905.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2019	131,498,373.0	160,792,627.0	5,483,732.0	48,856,474.0	89,060,462.0	13,406,042.0	-	15,827,676.0	-6,730,383.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2020	104,376,015.0	144,145,581.0	-	12,578,818.0	60,597,976.0	73,038,140.0	-	-	1,719,206.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2021	160,416,257.0	169,406,525.0	1,255,338.0	82,958,885.0	74,286,575.0	52,380,639.0	-	11,376,970.0	-10,268,532.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2022	206,822,127.0	215,660,208.0	15,651,362.0	113,732,630.0	89,979,391.0	28,118,793.0	-	-6,844,120.0	12,051,632.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2023	229,440,861.0	241,748,144.0	-	18,168,041.0	183,671,423.0	56,424,616.0	-	-6,317,423.0	-8,884,690.0	2,190,382.0
Guinness Nig. Plc	2024	299,489,774.0	226,130,077.0	-	54,766,776.0	222,684,738.0	2,161,466.0	-	-6,222,140.0	-123,799,125.0	2,190,382.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2013	45,709,382.0	55,437,478.0	2,843,520.0	27,503,156.0	18,553,083.0	-1,794,859.0	-	-6,603,263.0	7,774,043.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2014	55,084,305.0	63,830,439.0	3,351,564.0	28,059,339.0	20,605,248.0	6,431,524.0	-	-2,261,332.0	3,166,233.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2015	49,057,511.0	67,943,444.0	1,120,267.0	31,860,220.0	20,315,834.0	5,602,147.0	-	14,749,582.0	2,466,019.0	7,930,198.0
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2016	50,883,780.0	76,046,576.0	3,023,852.0	44,213,225.0	16,362,599.0	10,131,641.0	-	-6,046,484.0	7,521,745.0	7,930,198.0

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA and Anietie Sunday DAVID, MSc

Honeywell F. M. Plc	2017	53,227,891.0	113,151,715.0	4,304,955.0	26,318,698.0	52,334,665.0	-2,533,081.0	15,856,863.0	9,746,464.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2018	71,476,319.0	124,835,013.0	4,426,978.0	28,207,258.0	56,391,664.0	14,725,910.0	-5,975,524.0	-8,506,031.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2019	74,409,113.0	137,505,112.0	68,368.0	42,301,619.0	56,667,969.0	9,413,187.0	-5,649,275.0	-194,141.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2020	80,450,397.0	142,261,292.0	650,492.0	53,639,919.0	57,285,793.0	5,417,298.0	-2,595,247.0	-1,317,342.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2021	109,594,730.0	147,394,656.0	1,125,864.0	61,940,563.0	57,968,678.0	12,880,439.0	-741,759.0	-1,238,706.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2022	136,427,507.0	149,869,159.0	-983,812.0	67,182,805.0	56,429,751.0	-553,009.0	-1,300,350.0	4,698,685.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2023	147,350,739.0	164,999,977.0	256,113.0	90,173,174.0	32,976,289.0	-4,115,393.0	-6,915,289.0	5,368,495.0	7,930,198.0	
Honeywell F. M. Plc	2024	188,311,035.0	148,965,948.0	-	10,119,778.0	88,779,107.0	22,856,511.0	70,737,069.0	-1,801,355.0	-71,910,777.0	7,930,198.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)	
Int Breweries Plc	2013	17,388,632.0	23,036,762.0	2,327,342.0	7,859,335.0	9,380,173.0	-4,043,424.0	-6,718,935.0	11,486,402.0	3,262,526.0	
Int Breweries Plc	2014	18,493,907.0	24,370,540.0	2,105,500.0	6,604,447.0	11,269,923.0	6,258,083.0	-4,097,426.0	-2,809,671.0	3,294,250.0	
Int Breweries Plc	2015	20,649,295.0	30,171,590.0	2,395,178.0	9,975,208.0	12,168,259.0	3,151,232.0	-5,754,930.0	3,063,987.0	3,294,250.0	
Int Breweries Plc	2016	23,269,364.0	33,482,106.0	2,979,874.0	15,940,734.0	13,997,391.0	7,901,718.0	-3,946,605.0	-3,706,723.0	3,294,250.0	
Int Breweries Plc	2017	36,527,807.0	232,149,251.0	1,395,225.0	168,026,156.0	39,225,363.0	44,789,617.0	-	42,580,971.0	-11,016,915.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2018	120,610,825.0	310,278,920.0	3,866,298.0	118,879,435.0	35,160,923.0	-30,936,156.0	-	70,202,176.0	101,778,163.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2019	132,351,500.0	365,146,533.0	-27,790,666.0	204,106,062.0	7,463,701.0	41,686,120.0	-	58,647,254.0	59,795,928.0	8,595,862.0
Int Breweries Plc	2020	136,790,573.0	372,646,406.0	-12,365,082.0	217,921,521.0	151,733,857.0	52,227,989.0	-	29,959,433.0	-3,267,073.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2021	182,298,045.0	469,953,215.0	-17,656,510.0	325,679,434.0	135,303,901.0	52,041,595.0	-	86,496,101.0	50,448,845.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2022	218,650,266.0	484,251,740.0	-21,626,290.0	210,841,321.0	117,330,433.0	42,666,952.0	-	66,524,156.0	-6,919,758.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2023	264,278,299.0	733,113,172.0	-59,467,375.0	216,721,161.0	124,577,455.0	74,845,867.0	-	50,088,565.0	-31,379,888.0	26,862,068.0
Int Breweries Plc	2024	488,955,682.0	727,872,297.0	-	113,614,900.0	256,228,762.0	448,914,077.0	-	89,714,760.0	-81,053,542.0	32,519,250.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2013	11,701,741.0	3,623,417.0	225,145.0	1,634,103.0	1,605,717.0	1,125,731.0	-246,182.0	-27,030.0	178,200.0	
N Nig. Flour Plc	2014	11,392,017.0	3,266,615.0	233,545.0	1,187,714.0	1,773,912.0	-55,295.0	41,487.0	-85,327.0	178,200.0	
N Nig. Flour Plc	2015	10,529,075.0	2,225,405.0	-199,558.0	293,638.0	1,480,063.0	555,099.0	-68,046.0	-71,280.0	1,884,306.0	
N Nig. Flour Plc	2016	979,038.0	1,843,217.0	-197,240.0	90,908.0	1,250,937.0	-527,392.0	27,218.0	-53,460.0	777,038.0	

N Nig. Flour Plc	2017	1,330,536.0	4,337,444.0	-18,042.0	2,980,114.0	1,239,578.0	-871,530.0	-1,438,714.0	2,391,664.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2018	2,861,752.0	5,917,639.0	-60,988.0	3,374,312.0	1,174,262.0	-268,417.0	-268,819.0	623,605.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2019	4,149,917.0	4,992,912.0	-31,696.0	2,885,324.0	1,150,712.0	1,220,540.0	-105,361.0	-1,248,704.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2020	8,841,135.0	8,491,986.0	64,635.0	4,783,206.0	2,768,993.0	31,939,819.0	12,175,448.0	-38,154,460.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2021	8,667,751.0	7,365,270.0	69,919.0	3,833,773.0	2,787,771.0	-298,921.0	-31,233.0	-1,459,739.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2022	15,232,820.0	13,315,128.0	80,668.0	9,791,386.0	2,854,469.0	2,271,879.0	-514,610.0	-1,316,333.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2023	16,161,840.0	17,827,833.0	272,820.0	10,195,986.0	6,579,567.0	1,226,660.0	-179,945.0	-247,076.0	178,200.0
N Nig. Flour Plc	2024	22,951,365.0	17,924,446.0	1,525,895.0	8,766,651.0	8,077,739.0	1,663,173.0	-197,686.0	-238,765.0	178,200.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFF (N'000)	ESO (Unit)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	10,837,261.0	11,431,167.0	2,699,542.0	3,806,716.0	6,892,626.0	1,881,899.0	-2,362,290.0	-2,392,812.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	11,250,544.0	12,555,885.0	1,867,038.0	5,346,115.0	6,307,306.0	4,194,319.0	-2,114,952.0	-2,384,495.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	16,178,197.0	16,294,826.0	2,105,646.0	7,951,500.0	-1,324,719.0	4,007,770.0	-1,002,044.0	-1,344,784.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	18,291,792.0	24,603,267.0	2,415,183.0	15,124,953.0	2,415,183.0	2,238,497.0	-475,023.0	-1,814,862.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	27,064,325.0	30,123,247.0	2,565,896.0	16,615,330.0	-1,854,607.0	13,835,753.0	-4,924,362.0	-1,926,720.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	25,769,352.0	30,270,429.0	2,029,168.0	16,088,720.0	-3,974,158.0	1,021,757.0	-3,936,363.0	-3,974,158.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	27,487,788.0	38,668,792.0	1,845,243.0	18,742,264.0	11,089,285.0	6,090,389.0	-5,445,382.0	427,751.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	28,010,059.0	44,308,991.0	2,690,310.0	25,521,662.0	12,719,820.0	8,020,924.0	-3,984,916.0	-5,094,372.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	33,279,688.0	40,521,398.0	2,970,982.0	20,218,075.0	14,630,680.0	4,995,649.0	1,098,432.0	-1,675,884.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	58,786,251.0	55,530,771.0	5,496,248.0	30,489,559.0	19,042,366.0	3,499,588.0	-895,974.0	3,360,120.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	80,828,373.0	83,591,991.0	13,728,369.0	49,659,750.0	27,471,858.0	20,049,817.0	-893,510.0	-6,321,250.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2024	120,387,151.0	78,502,487.0	15,583,602.0	26,337,166.0	43,055,460.0	4,164,628.0	-562,308.0	-4,217,064.0	2,702,426.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	133,084,076.0	108,207,480.0	22,258,279.0	32,817,482.0	23,004,468.0	35,216,402.0	-7,030,198.0	-18,283,766.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	143,328,982.0	106,062,067.0	22,235,640.0	44,103,244.0	30,056,784.0	23,495,038.0	-7,263,538.0	-27,481,104.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	151,271,526.0	119,215,053.0	23,736,777.0	59,731,857.0	38,007,074.0	39,877,436.0	-7,228,711.0	-22,491,122.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	181,910,977.0	169,585,932.0	7,924,968.0	121,033,434.0	30,878,075.0	61,484,847.0	-2,842,594.0	-20,070,185.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	244,151,411.0	146,804,128.0	33,723,730.0	79,680,495.0	44,878,177.0	19,235,881.0	-2,433,312.0	-56,574,372.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	266,274,621.0	162,334,442.0	43,008,026.0	92,117,501.0	50,220,486.0	74,618,791.0	10,984,275.0	-60,690,925.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	284,035,255.0	193,374,314.0	45,683,113.0	125,535,430.0	45,557,630.0	49,945,530.0	12,328,813.0	-47,743,062.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	287,084,087.0	246,184,996.0	39,212,025.0	166,030,351.0	29,296,984.0	97,196,104.0	15,718,617.0	-27,018,843.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	351,822,329.0	310,238,504.0	40,037,277.0	195,517,985.0	21,378,209.0	65,927,085.0	19,969,328.0	-4,449,023.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	446,819,260.0	415,044,031.0	48,965,488.0	218,404,562.0	30,291,224.0	-4,432,963.0	22,868,150.0	44,241,769.0	792,656.0

Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	547,118,754.0	581,774,407.0	-79,473,781.0	290,637,709.0	-	78,035,156.0	82,702,831.0	-	55,112,317.0	21,293,339.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2024	958,814,739.0	858,698,352.0	164,592,022.0	401,426,871.0	-	92,289,917.0	5,858,732.0	-	69,160,262.0	-84,244,062.0	792,656.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFF (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Nascon Allied Plc	2013	10,837,261.0	11,431,167.0	2,699,542.0	3,806,716.0	6,892,626.0	1,881,899.0	-2,362,290.0	-2,392,812.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2014	11,250,544.0	12,555,885.0	1,867,038.0	5,346,115.0	6,307,306.0	4,194,319.0	-2,114,952.0	-2,384,495.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2015	16,178,197.0	16,294,826.0	2,105,646.0	7,951,500.0	-1,324,719.0	4,007,770.0	-1,002,044.0	-1,344,784.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2016	18,291,792.0	24,603,267.0	2,415,183.0	15,124,953.0	2,415,183.0	2,238,497.0	-475,023.0	-1,814,862.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2017	27,064,325.0	30,123,247.0	2,565,896.0	16,615,330.0	-1,854,607.0	13,835,753.0	-4,924,362.0	-1,926,720.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2018	25,769,352.0	30,270,429.0	2,029,168.0	16,088,720.0	-3,974,158.0	1,021,757.0	-3,936,363.0	-3,974,158.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2019	27,487,788.0	38,668,792.0	1,845,243.0	18,742,264.0	11,089,285.0	6,090,389.0	-5,445,382.0	427,751.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2020	28,010,059.0	44,308,991.0	2,690,310.0	25,521,662.0	12,719,820.0	8,020,924.0	-3,984,916.0	-5,094,372.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2021	33,279,688.0	40,521,398.0	2,970,982.0	20,218,075.0	14,630,680.0	4,995,649.0	1,098,432.0	-1,675,884.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2022	58,786,251.0	55,530,771.0	5,496,248.0	30,489,559.0	19,042,366.0	3,499,588.0	-895,974.0	3,360,120.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2023	80,828,373.0	83,591,991.0	13,728,369.0	49,659,750.0	27,471,858.0	20,049,817.0	-893,510.0	-6,321,250.0	2,649,438.0
Nascon Allied Plc	2024	120,387,151.0	78,502,487.0	15,583,602.0	26,337,166.0	43,055,460.0	4,164,628.0	-562,308.0	-4,217,064.0	2,702,426.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2013	133,084,076.0	108,207,480.0	22,258,279.0	32,817,482.0	23,004,468.0	35,216,402.0	-7,030,198.0	-18,283,766.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2014	143,328,982.0	106,062,067.0	22,235,640.0	44,103,244.0	30,056,784.0	23,495,038.0	-7,263,538.0	-27,481,104.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2015	151,271,526.0	119,215,053.0	23,736,777.0	59,731,857.0	38,007,074.0	39,877,436.0	-7,228,711.0	-22,491,122.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2016	181,910,977.0	169,585,932.0	7,924,968.0	121,033,434.0	30,878,075.0	61,484,847.0	-2,842,594.0	-20,070,185.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2017	244,151,411.0	146,804,128.0	33,723,730.0	79,680,495.0	44,878,177.0	19,235,881.0	-2,433,312.0	-56,574,372.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2018	266,274,621.0	162,334,442.0	43,008,026.0	92,117,501.0	50,220,486.0	74,618,791.0	-10,984,275.0	-60,690,925.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2019	284,035,255.0	193,374,314.0	45,683,113.0	125,535,430.0	45,557,630.0	49,945,530.0	-12,328,813.0	-47,743,062.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2020	287,084,087.0	246,184,996.0	39,212,025.0	166,030,351.0	29,296,984.0	97,196,104.0	-15,718,617.0	-27,018,843.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2021	351,822,329.0	310,238,504.0	40,037,277.0	195,517,985.0	21,378,209.0	65,927,085.0	-19,969,328.0	-4,449,023.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2022	446,819,260.0	415,044,031.0	48,965,488.0	218,404,562.0	30,291,224.0	-4,432,963.0	-22,868,150.0	44,241,769.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2023	547,118,754.0	581,774,407.0	-79,473,781.0	290,637,709.0	-78,035,156.0	82,702,831.0	-55,112,317.0	21,293,339.0	792,656.0
Nestle Nig. Plc	2024	958,814,739.0	858,698,352.0	164,592,022.0	401,426,871.0	-92,289,917.0	5,858,732.0	-69,160,262.0	-84,244,062.0	792,656.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2013	71,343,088.0	72,296,420.0	5,321,187.0	21,397,087.0	46,436,857.0	9,738,717.0	-1,400,485.0	-1,989,316.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2014	72,905,679.0	70,965,735.0	5,082,747.0	23,952,048.0	42,538,582.0	7,451,110.0	-2,699,576.0	-9,145,712.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2015	73,126,070.0	48,106,661.0	2,168,867.0	17,763,887.0	26,584,929.0	3,705,398.0	-1,978,982.0	-3,941,990.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2016	69,527,537.0	56,261,100.0	389,999.0	18,360,626.0	33,792,289.0	9,331,347.0	-3,104,797.0	-3,275,295.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2017	54,761,729.0	73,039,610.0	2,235,631.0	35,003,206.0	34,076,230.0	6,576,014.0	-4,716,888.0	-2,401,225.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2018	58,483,029.0	74,576,119.0	1,630,557.0	37,159,730.0	33,750,379.0	13,245,662.0	-2,171,014.0	-2,897,264.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2019	47,200,919.0	64,315,676.0	578,355.0	26,277,664.0	33,816,582.0	-8,469,686.0	-931,909.0	-771,440.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2020	38,939,223.0	59,486,850.0	5,966,995.0	28,638,942.0	23,896,811.0	7,365,761.0	489,244.0	-1,268,813.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2021	47,832,559.0	69,368,707.0	817,322.0	39,826,778.0	23,045,466.0	11,456,860.0	-6,920,410.0	-538,500.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2022	58,264,660.0	79,875,535.0	1,779,704.0	50,611,339.0	23,872,147.0	3,685,863.0	20,423,975.0	-1,106,286.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2023	67,423,111.0	110,826,000.0	8,528,436.0	82,153,532.0	28,677,468.0	3,865,678.0	3,482,684.0	15,893,610.0	3,970,476.0
PZ Cusson Nig. Plc	2024	90,810,486.0	118,112,517.0	45,575,943.0	74,387,249.0	16,746,699.0	58,904,035.0	5,040,399.0	152,740.0	3,970,476.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2013	60,004,119.0	43,754,114.0	4,724,429.0	28,072,640.0	9,347,922.0	11,680,745.0	-5,858,527.0	-2,707,936.0	3,783,298.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2014	55,754,309.0	45,736,255.0	2,412,343.0	31,857,164.0	7,478,808.0	-1,824,795.0	-3,834,183.0	2,427,299.0	3,783,298.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2015	59,221,748.0	50,172,484.0	1,192,366.0	34,697,653.0	8,003,253.0	15,589,947.0	-4,684,542.0	-3,787,354.0	3,783,298.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2016	69,777,061.0	72,491,309.0	3,071,885.0	53,513,389.0	11,689,943.0	5,990,506.0	-3,883,493.0	12,467,556.0	3,783,298.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2017	85,193,369.0	121,084,365.0	7,450,085.0	36,695,307.0	75,908,375.0	6,037,791.0	-3,353,153.0	40,334,816.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2018	92,899,969.0	131,843,373.0	10,552,140.0	43,167,053.0	82,789,543.0	6,943,170.0	3,093,503.0	-3,434,762.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2019	60,486,835.0	103,677,519.0	-7,419,674.0	34,808,084.0	66,528,350.0	11,524,317.0	-4,333,894.0	-5,825,150.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2020	61,959,678.0	91,517,538.0	-3,965,921.0	27,798,857.0	62,129,120.0	2,401,016.0	-819,984.0	-428,898.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2021	70,523,695.0	108,288,535.0	3,409,174.0	40,217,689.0	65,761,668.0	20,089,953.0	-927,920.0	-363,078.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2022	88,570,826.0	125,389,892.0	4,467,084.0	55,377,157.0	67,564,716.0	12,031,343.0	669,429.0	-1,827,837.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2023	103,879,730.0	116,302,344.0	8,439,895.0	33,797,046.0	74,509,103.0	-3,784,529.0	1,542,176.0	-8,267,868.0	5,745,006.0
Unilever Nig. Plc	2024	149,522,596.0	141,646,696.0	15,143,154.0	50,847,675.0	85,106,080.0	14,547,614.0	-2,618,208.0	-7,178,932.0	5,745,006.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	
Champion B. Plc	2013	2,233,259.0	9,137,716.0	-1,178,025.0	13,683,275.0	-4,608,386.0	1,058,062.0	-933,273.0	0.0	900,000.0	
Champion B. Plc	2014	3,302,383.0	9,592,381.0	-754,523.0	3,578,929.0	5,870,431.0	1,008,118.0	-277,159.0	-313,807.0	7,200,000.0	
Champion B. Plc	2015	3,501,845.0	10,329,160.0	77,140.0	3,073,998.0	7,121,637.0	1,287,183.0	-653,727.0	0.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2016	3,864,943.0	9,961,240.0	530,389.0	2,208,173.0	7,670,860.0	368,019.0	-418,573.0	0.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2017	4,777,313.0	10,088,861.0	517,562.0	1,627,573.0	8,135,460.0	47,221.0	-855,138.0	0.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2018	4,763,757.0	10,487,010.0	-263,807.0	2,305,491.0	7,935,532.0	1,142,454.0	-1,267,856.0	0.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2019	6,927,177.0	10,981,383.0	168,508.0	2,564,456.0	8,031,796.0	1,637,027.0	-1,120,954.0	0.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2020	7,051,806.0	11,368,517.0	158,793.0	2,251,657.0	8,042,994.0	1,976,064.0	-1,620,959.0	-31,826.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2021	10,518,497.0	13,486,815.0	984,233.0	3,435,750.0	9,219,643.0	3,759,396.0	-1,833,581.0	-79,022.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2022	12,288,893.0	15,453,585.0	1,585,978.0	2,926,961.0	11,119,384.0	2,260,174.0	-2,851,121.0	-92,272.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2023	12,704,274.0	20,533,079.0	370,563.0	7,968,406.0	11,195,299.0	5,822,757.0	-6,581,822.0	1,014,875.0	7,829,496.0	
Champion B. Plc	2024	20,890,735.0	21,345,197.0	816,995.0	9,217,856.0	12,056,086.0	5,183,808.0	-808,846.0	-2,509,526.0	8,947,996.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2013	102,467,361.0	87,112,182.0	13,537,612.0	26,246,090.0	57,125,832.0	-12,175,509.0	-6,000,000.0	0.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2014	94,103,677.0	97,287,804.0	11,908,690.0	33,220,434.0	51,413,720.0	-5,595,694.0	-5,200,000.0	0.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2015	100,092,221.0	97,287,804.0	12,659,855.0	34,532,088.0	58,526,202.0	10,655,422.0	-3,540,092.0	-4,300,000.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2016	167,409,161.0	106,671,333.0	14,198,693.0	35,516,958.0	66,388,057.0	34,548,986.0	-2,109,157.0	-8,500,000.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2017	198,120,639.0	198,064,664.0	37,822,609.0	91,644,487.0	99,207,358.0	26,484,287.0	-5,775,419.0	-13,228,332.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2018	146,549,176.0	178,523,711.0	25,830,941.0	66,033,588.0	107,180,126.0	-7,265,964.0	-2,840,308.0	-15,000,000.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2019	78,608,142.0	174,646,907.0	12,869,456.0	62,487,298.0	106,849,582.0	-7,751,585.0	-3,566,735.0	-15,000,000.0	12,000,000.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2020	206,360,656.0	259,280,544.0	31,370,659.0	122,752,272.0	125,302,902.0	43,818,395.0	-9,232,795.0	-13,854,483.0	12,146,878.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2021	276,054,781.0	349,382,869.0	22,660,116.0	207,221,431.0	129,830,169.0	106,378,342.0	-	13,414,678.0	-35,303,840.0	12,146,878.0
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2022	403,245,988.0	490,969,836.0	54,346,390.0	305,170,514.0	172,029,685.0	108,946,471.0	15,455,034.0	-20,889,104.0	12,146,878.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2023	441,452,953.0	601,040,524.0	-71,999,460.0	518,900,557.0	81,809,910.0	6,199,772.0	-6,092,670.0	-21,474,246.0	12,146,878.0	
Dang. S. Ref. Plc	2024	665,689,763.0	1,018,344,271.0	190,866,449.0	798,723,006.0	179,695,466.0	370,325,889.0	-	24,868,544.0	225,971,693.0	12,146,878.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2013	15,519,856.0	9,376,225.0	562,350.0	5,212,095.0	3,267,313.0	1,289,816.0	-373,437.0	-678,657.0	409,500.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2014	15,519,856.0	11,032,131.0	394,690.0	6,664,532.0	3,747,004.0	1,635,578.0	-123,294.0	-1,202,695.0	409,500.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2015	15,155,102.0	11,734,739.0	196,640.0	6,756,676.0	3,802,832.0	494,129.0	-442,487.0	-387,001.0	982,800.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2016	12,189,558.0	13,098,732.0	412,386.0	7,770,121.0	4,375,223.0	-1,557,076.0	-364,785.0	1,500,767.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2017	15,921,022.0	12,974,483.0	190,540.0	7,622,014.0	4,463,206.0	2,090,468.0	-62,005.0	-1,925,303.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2018	17,612,291.0	15,156,727.0	486,120.0	7,884,358.0	4,822,994.0	-167,810.0	-60,195.0	1,512,711.0	1,042,070.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2019	20,330,040.0	12,358,342.0	1,574,909.0	4,462,649.0	5,932,044.0	4,837,585.0	-138,815.0	-3,910,336.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2020	21,521,097.0	19,802,249.0	3,456,694.0	7,654,807.0	8,687,013.0	4,806,873.0	-786,167.0	1,678,498.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2021	32,007,979.0	29,693,840.0	4,384,859.0	15,235,021.0	12,401,122.0	202,869.0	-514,462.0	4,029,988.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2022	42,128,595.0	36,913,111.0	4,411,111.0	20,213,120.0	15,013,073.0	434,146.0	255,479.0	307,953.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2023	47,723,375.0	46,673,301.0	3,418,992.0	29,080,166.0	16,178,032.0	1,793,499.0	-175,266.0	4,599,872.0	1,250,844.0
Vitafoam Nig. Plc	2024	73,492,246.0	45,907,461.0	-906,511.0	18,701,228.0	21,624,873.0	1,635,176.0	646,461.0	17,945,376.0	1,250,844.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)
Berger Paints Plc	2013	2,710,986.0	3,627,598.0	257,580.0	798,623.0	2,476,257.0	-165,600.0	42,717.0	512,599.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2014	3,082,930.0	3,640,145.0	148,808.0	816,531.0	2,459,830.0	-462,336.0	-30,573.0	-223,590.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2015	3,022,264.0	3,895,870.0	330,316.0	1,143,703.0	2,587,330.0	514,780.0	-163,177.0	-172,740.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2016	2,602,824.0	4,102,265.0	224,007.0	1,306,347.0	2,604,181.0	758,941.0	-710,249.0	-162,484.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2017	3,012,648.0	4,311,424.0	246,276.0	1,080,532.0	2,641,145.0	316,725.0	-191,106.0	143,179.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2018	3,377,223.0	4,535,299.0	320,509.0	1,285,038.0	2,813,052.0	440,335.0	-342,333.0	-274,603.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2019	3,584,804.0	5,066,449.0	448,733.0	1,488,025.0	3,073,400.0	396,290.0	-318,000.0	-271,811.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2020	3,837,582.0	4,971,872.0	146,028.0	1,328,867.0	3,146,972.0	454,612.0	-163,667.0	-151,034.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2021	4,964,796.0	5,110,669.0	135,635.0	1,439,061.0	3,230,703.0	265,919.0	-104,157.0	-300,732.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2022	6,331,634.0	5,528,528.0	208,670.0	1,690,196.0	3,323,445.0	571,518.0	-71,430.0	-221,879.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2023	7,910,181.0	6,610,970.0	468,797.0	2,056,868.0	3,531,401.0	408,196.0	-141,191.0	35,194.0	289,824.0
Berger Paints Plc	2024	10,739,502.0	7,534,781.0	614,960.0	2,835,193.0	3,855,900.0	229,939.0	-486,498.0	-329,797.0	289,824.0
Beta Glass Plc	2013	14,096,123.0	27,166,481.0	1,473,574.0	9,423,313.0	13,753,157.0	2,922,972.0	-1,332,973.0	-588,349.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2014	16,632,879.0	26,928,387.0	2,390,223.0	7,673,957.0	15,952,981.0	4,341,369.0	-1,453,049.0	-1,925,533.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2015	15,953,224.0	27,171,069.0	1,991,127.0	5,527,007.0	17,578,125.0	4,842,441.0	-3,668,180.0	-344,143.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2016	19,091,192.0	33,184,130.0	3,799,393.0	6,990,457.0	21,474,964.0	4,912,545.0	-667,297.0	-221,871.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2017	22,186,258.0	38,211,613.0	4,115,142.0	9,042,953.0	25,145,114.0	1,076,544.0	-2,216,587.0	-22,533.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2018	26,321,014.0	46,079,629.0	5,052,805.0	13,723,312.0	29,627,573.0	8,614,946.0	-6,487,730.0	-436,830.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2019	29,412,252.0	52,080,362.0	5,580,220.0	15,032,650.0	34,558,001.0	5,405,503.0	-5,465,631.0	958,503.0	499,972.0

Jeremiah Patrick EDET, PhD, ACA and Anietie Sunday DAVID, MSc

Beta Glass Plc	2020	25,637,010.0	53,963,634.0	3,466,670.0	14,812,299.0	37,189,718.0	3,361,039.0	-2,554,948.0	147,350.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2021	36,982,815.0	63,112,410.0	5,457,671.0	17,400,029.0	42,127,418.0	7,405,003.0	-3,017,141.0	-41,035.0	499,972.0
Beta Glass Plc	2022	54,340,363.0	75,944,552.0	4,685,414.0	26,142,597.0	46,263,350.0	1,312,596.0	-4,740,355.0	3,609,199.0	599,966.0
Beta Glass Plc	2023	62,905,451.0	106,851,898.0	6,442,223.0	3,538,605.0	52,005,006.0	11,385,599.0	-12,142,676.0	2,954,918.0	599,966.0
Beta Glass Plc	2024	117,580,184.0	137,352,197.0	13,626,830.0	64,940,404.0	64,791,883.0	17,515,552.0	-19,937,854.0	13,153,438.0	599,966.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (N'000)	TA (N'000)	PAT (N'000)	CL (N'000)	TE (N'000)	NCFO (N'000)	NCFI (N'000)	NCFE (N'000)	ESO (Unit)	
BUA Cement Plc	2013	15,311,004.0	15,058,476.0	1,559,031.0	4,101,944.0	8,284,619.0	2,071,903.0	-1,157,105.0	-439,656.0	1,256,678.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2014	15,119,051.0	15,780,013.0	1,918,362.0	3,496,155.0	9,445,658.0	1,863,994.0	-1,786,509.0	-258,179.0	1,256,678.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2015	13,037,847.0	17,146,883.0	1,201,108.0	4,145,323.0	10,144,768.0	2,569,229.0	-2,260,421.0	223,636.0	1,256,678.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2016	14,087,553.0	20,030,222.0	1,253,805.0	5,501,981.0	11,493,272.0	2,799,490.0	-980,194.0	-360,490.0	1,256,678.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2017	19,588,261.0	24,648,676.0	3,223,854.0	7,165,954.0	14,412,207.0	3,625,888.0	-2,571,250.0	-384,459.0	1,256,678.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2018	31,721,962.0	347,746,456.0	5,731,321.0	11,554,244.0	333,487,688.0	1,362,117.0	-2,733,048.0	-166,894.0	13,143,502.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2019	32,148,368.0	356,753,843.0	7,283,413.0	13,448,729.0	340,771,502.0	10,964,758.0	-6,717,917.0	-204,265.0	13,143,502.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2020	209,443,487.0	766,302,578.0	72,344,336.0	208,100,189.0	375,954,728.0	65,112,598.0	128,849,627.0	1,728,508,889.0	33,864,354.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2021	257,327,091.0	728,507,473.0	90,079,011.0	145,355,120.0	398,116,748.0	198,957,257.0	-58,076,721.0	-214,503,647.0	33,864,354.0	
BUA Cement Plc	2022	360,989,105.0	874,011,884.0	101,010,626.0	25,756,156.0	411,112,542.0	149,573,594.0	-	102,275,234.0	-61,628,432.0	33,864,354.0
BUA Cement Plc	2023	459,998,999.0	1,215,686,377.0	69,454,750.0	377,037,627.0	385,224,150.0	150,052,489.0	-	104,119,517.0	8,005,350.0	33,864,354.0
BUA Cement Plc	2024	876,469,849.0	1,570,351,865.0	73,909,235.0	574,554,529.0	388,548,235.0	405,253,085.0	-	272,678,983.0	-370,993,558.0	33,864,354.0
Cutix Plc	2013	1,929,477.0	1,073,865.0	151,423.0	399,744.0	597,554.0	193,539.0	-67,922.0	-105,291.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2014	2,234,959.0	1,744,670.0	207,116.0	696,154.0	699,703.0	126,655.0	-504,907.0	-156,882.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2015	2,358,412.0	1,968,813.0	149,209.0	922,892.0	743,711.0	222,355.0	-217,408.0	-17,784.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2016	2,835,862.0	1,891,720.0	190,551.0	756,297.0	870,217.0	644,996.0	-24,045.0	-563,973.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2017	3,675,712.0	2,329,792.0	257,497.0	1,112,406.0	1,013,969.0	190,068.0	-45,474.0	-108,335.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2018	5,057,374.0	2,836,262.0	440,295.0	1,359,513.0	1,299,292.0	609,478.0	-227,573.0	-393,031.0	880,662.0	
Cutix Plc	2019	5,434,107.0	2,861,339.0	477,070.0	1,032,494.0	1,613,091.0	427,399.0	-197,527.0	-221,616.0	3,522,644.0	
Cutix Plc	2020	5,025,500.0	3,627,990.0	393,053.0	1,313,836.0	1,805,638.0	90,130.0	-100,166.0	65,044.0	3,522,644.0	
Cutix Plc	2021	6,745,521.0	4,801,452.0	601,627.0	2,308,511.0	2,214,333.0	295,955.0	-429,239.0	74,282.0	3,522,644.0	
Cutix Plc	2022	7,852,391.0	5,086,471.0	790,467.0	2,109,127.0	2,767,160.0	1,203,416.0	-248,645.0	-942,769.0	3,522,644.0	
Cutix Plc	2023	9,225,071.0	5,796,790.0	792,132.0	2,332,152.0	3,232,801.0	514,849.0	-263,253.0	-258,985.0	3,522,644.0	
Cutix Plc	2024	12,167,838.0	7,212,949.0	1,075,397.0	2,667,419.0	3,880,083.0	985,994.0	-396,790.0	-466,447.0	3,522,644.0	

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)	
Dang. Cem. Plc	2013	371,551,567.0	821,699,780.0	210,262,754.0	150,992,846.0	571,562,826.0	275,953,727.0	-	168,619,000.0	-81,589,914.0	17,040,508.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2014	371,534,117.0	963,441,064.0	185,814,123.0	205,829,677.0	638,543,114.0	195,608,275.0	-	162,125,000.0	-84,576,991.0	17,040,508.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2015	389,215,000.0	1,124,475,000.0	213,171,000.0	140,586,000.0	748,479,000.0	249,235,000.0	-	131,571,000.0	-116,052,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2016	426,129,000.0	1,502,564,000.0	368,205,000.0	390,226,000.0	981,367,000.0	236,064,000.0	-	75,879,000.0	-112,637,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2017	552,364,000.0	1,611,087,000.0	254,630,000.0	343,956,000.0	991,017,000.0	297,968,000.0	-	51,278,000.0	-209,732,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2018	618,301,000.0	1,721,974,000.0	481,456,000.0	284,759,000.0	1,293,548,000.0	337,186,000.0	-	94,146,000.0	-236,528,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2019	610,247,000.0	1,823,984,000.0	261,349,000.0	410,575,000.0	1,282,249,000.0	333,484,000.0	-	124,219,000.0	-262,458,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2020	719,945,000.0	2,116,060,000.0	352,609,000.0	538,613,000.0	1,352,377,000.0	398,290,000.0	-	199,335,000.0	-185,894,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2021	993,399,000.0	2,582,298,000.0	381,100,000.0	837,858,000.0	1,461,472,000.0	595,746,000.0	-	170,226,770.0	-290,558,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2022	1,205,401,000.0	2,658,463,000.0	402,857,000.0	775,840,000.0	1,491,535,000.0	364,185,000.0	-	118,485,000.0	-380,581,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2023	1,297,639,000.0	3,070,468,000.0	490,323,000.0	1,127,236,000.0	1,602,964,000.0	406,759,000.0	-	83,782,000.0	-336,517,000.0	17,040,000.0
Dang. Cem. Plc	2024	2,192,695,000.0	5,194,814,000.0	1,027,217,000.0	1,746,596,000.0	2,127,616,000.0	653,366,000.0	-	830,938,000.0	-223,683,000.0	16,874,000.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2013	97,174,505.0	159,866,917.0	28,022,200.0	39,334,496.0	92,641,665.0	35,452,200.0	-	1,235,097.0	-22,837,480.0	3,001,600.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2014	105,848,657.0	343,627,558.0	28,360,146.0	36,526,476.0	276,664,338.0	37,737,758.0	-	33,050,495.0	-23,249,783.0	4,404,176.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2015	114,558,245.0	381,272,953.0	29,837,395.0	47,557,407.0	302,601,869.0	33,733,822.0	-	2,093,919.0	-33,412,891.0	4,554,902.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2016	87,198,416.0	537,598,212.0	20,778,348.0	112,592,247.0	340,094,143.0	-30,907,024.0	-	5,048,387.0	13,459,929.0	5,480,734.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2017	177,170,362.0	616,169,940.0	-13,223,626.0	282,455,768.0	264,768,895.0	1,778,571.0	-	6,706,392.0	20,729,761.0	5,575,776.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2018	187,043,475.0	577,692,296.0	4,141,764.0	173,870,677.0	255,743,725.0	39,125,112.0	-	11,801,206.0	-40,615,290.0	8,673,430.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2019	188,407,004.0	500,081,653.0	22,721,616.0	89,216,038.0	361,421,559.0	77,275,692.0	-	5,918,974.0	-39,659,029.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2020	202,530,359.0	505,332,716.0	28,714,884.0	124,522,776.0	373,974,933.0	48,655,540.0	-	6,542,358.0	-27,528,292.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2021	262,299,071.0	534,054,123.0	53,455,912.0	133,856,097.0	395,349,470.0	-	-	748,175,715.0	-12,487,697.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2022	340,633,999.0	609,182,343.0	55,032,460.0	169,932,087.0	434,275,803.0	-91,308,889.0	-	19,890,609.0	-10,792,645.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2023	372,513,521.0	689,780,550.0	48,056,437.0	2,122,659,591.0	450,120,336.0	147,011,474.0	-	32,680,014.0	-63,818,929.0	16,107,798.0
Lafarge Africa Plc	2024	651,024,707.0	997,632,873.0	99,687,811.0	411,175,322.0	519,251,658.0	200,924,994.0	-	61,560,354.0	-72,445,537.0	16,107,798.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Table B: Raw Data Collected for the Study from 2013 to 2024 Continued

Company	Year	REV (₦'000)	TA (₦'000)	PAT (₦'000)	CL (₦'000)	TE (₦'000)	NCFO (₦'000)	NCFI (₦'000)	NCFE (₦'000)	ESO (Unit)
Meyer Paints Plc	2013	1,500,112.0	2,597,517.0	-26,149.0	750,754.0	622,382.0	246,381.0	21,541.0	-209,268.0	325,000.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2014	1,340,104.0	2,435,368.0	-33,106.0	690,701.0	581,626.0	140,348.0	-16,849.0	-213,494.0	325,000.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2015	1,187,236.0	2,301,121.0	73,230.0	594,689.0	638,100.0	11,864.0	101.0	-110,431.0	291,490.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2016	1,091,000.0	2,178,705.0	-214,402.0	784,368.0	423,698.0	-36,215.0	3,291.0	1,196.0	291,490.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2017	1,097,061.0	1,890,966.0	-267,739.0	1,273,952.0	302,969.0	-20,822.0	-24,054.0	58,593.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2018	970,134.0	1,839,132.0	319,297.0	1,053,881.0	621,063.0	28,336.0	-1,831.0	-21,642.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2019	1,106,116.0	3,720,214.0	-13,493.0	2,964,620.0	607,570.0	1,949,902.0	-131,402.0	-361,214.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2020	827,599.0	2,952,080.0	1,108,506.0	1,272,315.0	1,716,076.0	-2,341,267.0	3,240,078.0	10,047.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2021	1,118,098.0	1,986,513.0	33,673.0	956,666.0	1,003,158.0	-310,230.0	79,002.0	-762,108.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2022	1,435,032.0	1,907,674.0	393,617.0	468,779.0	1,396,775.0	-153,867.0	73,173.0	11,484.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2023	2,266,791.0	2,424,767.0	235,969.0	756,395.0	1,632,744.0	105,719.0	89,675.0	-166.0	497,728.0
Meyer Paints Plc	2024	3,123,957.0	2,813,107.0	295,406.0	988,432.0	1,778,800.0	30,653.0	194,453.0	-170,228.0	497,728.0
CAP Plc	2013	6,195,824.0	3,035,012.0	1,416,795.0	1,684,573.0	1,268,148.0	1,448,652.0	18,245.0	-1,276,649.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2014	6,987,604.0	3,080,882.0	1,662,426.0	1,825,999.0	1,180,573.0	1,340,956.0	42,304.0	-1,749,978.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2015	7,056,876.0	3,409,300.0	1,739,559.0	1,833,838.0	1,520,133.0	261,700.0	138,767.0	-1,027,010.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2016	6,813,984.0	4,915,999.0	1,603,357.0	2,495,428.0	2,283,490.0	134,054.0	-60,724.0	-475,653.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2017	7,113,950.0	5,013,990.0	1,498,730.0	2,671,721.0	2,242,220.0	1,804,682.0	40,935.0	-1,356,969.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2018	7,670,315.0	6,311,246.0	2,029,343.0	3,375,254.0	2,808,939.0	1,742,787.0	163,111.0	-1,930,995.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2019	8,410,650.0	6,760,961.0	1,742,088.0	4,069,187.0	2,521,684.0	1,753,000.0	152,893.0	-1,930,995.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2020	8,876,191.0	8,526,076.0	1,223,124.0	4,781,268.0	3,744,808.0	990,962.0	137,226.0	322,892.0	700,000.0
CAP Plc	2021	14,207,818.0	12,115,919.0	1,122,583.0	7,532,448.0	4,409,788.0	-1,278,694.0	-395,375.0	-1,502,309.0	788,260.0
CAP Plc	2022	19,208,470.0	13,406,204.0	2,376,208.0	6,470,057.0	6,599,601.0	1,340,259.0	-540,163.0	388,990.0	814,748.0
CAP Plc	2023	23,890,279.0	15,373,521.0	2,514,737.0	6,906,761.0	7,969,707.0	3,581,356.0	-327,636.0	-2,018,374.0	814,748.0
CAP Plc	2024	36,362,182.0	19,677,179.0	3,807,258.0	7,910,709.0	10,636,487.0	5,034,673.0	-1,605,723.0	-1,410,640.0	814,748.0

Source: Financial Statements of Quoted Industrial Goods Companies in Nigeria for Various Years

Where SP=Share Price, NAPS=Net Assets Per Share, NCFPS=Net Cash Flows Per Share, EPS=Earnings Per Share, ATR=Assets Turnover Ratio, EAR=Equity-to-Assets Ratio, REV=Revenue, TA=Total Assets, PAT=Profit After Tax, CL=Current Liabilities, TE=Total Equity, NCFO= Net Cash Flows from Operating Activities, NCFI= Net Cash Flows from Investing Activities, NCFE=Net Cash Flows from Financing Activities and ESO=Equity Shares Outstanding